

A Novel Structured Argumentation for Logical Reasoning

Abstract

This is a technical report, in which we provide notions, definitions, and results in detail. The complete version will be provided in a separate journal submission.

1. Introduction

Argumentation is a useful approach for modelling reasoning with conflicting and dynamic information (Dung, Kowalski, & Toni, 2009; Dung, 1995). Those are divided into three approaches:

- *Argumentation approach based on Deductive logic*: Various works propose instantiations of abstract argumentation (AFs) for Datalog[±] (Arioua, Croitoru, & Vesic, 2017; Yun, Vesic, & Croitoru, 2020), Description Logic (Zhang & Lin, 2013) or Classical Logic (D’Agostino & Modgil, 2018), focusing on the translation of KBs to argumentation without considering explanations. In (Ho, Arch-int, Acar, Schlobach, & Arch-int, 2022), explanations can be viewed as dialectical trees defined abstractly, requiring a deep understanding of formal arguments and trees, making the work impractical for non-experts. In (Yun et al., 2020; Yun, Vesic, & Croitoru, 2018), argumentation with collective attacks is proposed to capture non-binary conflicts in Datalog[±], i.e., assuming that every conflict has more than two formulas.
- *Sequent-based argumentation* (Arieli & Straßer, 2019) and its extension (*Hypersequent-based argumentation*) (Borg, Arieli, & Straßer, 2017), using *Propositional Logic*, provide non-monotonic extensions for Gentzen-style proof systems in terms of argumentation-based. Moreover, the authors conclude by wishing future work to include “the study of more expressive formalisms, like those that are based on first-order logics” (Arieli & Straßer, 2019).
- *Rule-based argumentation*: *DeLP/DeLP* with *collective attacks* are introduced for defeasible logic programming (García & Simari, 2014; Alsinet, Béjar, & Godo, 2010). However, in (Yun et al., 2020), the authors claim that they cannot instantiate DeLP for Datalog[±], since DeLP only considers ground rules. In (Prakken & Vreeswijk, 2002; Modgil & Prakken, 2014), *ASPIC/ASPIC+* is introduced for defeasible logic. Following (Amgoud, 2012), the logical formalism in ASPIC is ill-defined, i.e., the contrariness relation is not general enough to consider n-ary constraints. This issue is stated in (Yun et al., 2020) for Datalog[±], namely, the ASPIC cannot be directly instantiated with Datalog[±]. The reasons behind this are that Datalog[±] does not have the negation and the contrariness function of ASPIC is not general for this language.

Notable works include assumption-based argumentation (ABA) (Dung et al., 2009) and ABA with collective attack (Dimopoulos, Dvorák, König, Rapberger, Ulbricht, & Woltran, 2024), which are applied for default logic and logic programming. However,

ABAs ignore cases of the inferred assumptions conflicting, which is allowed in the existential rules, Description Logic and Logic Programming with Negation as Failure in the Head. We call the ABAs "flat ABAs". In (Schulz & Toni, 2016), "flat" ABAs link to Answer Set Programming but only consider a single conflict for each assumption. In (Rapberger, Ulbricht, & Toni, 2024; Lehtonen, Rapberger, Toni, Ulbricht, & Wallner, 2024), "Non-flat" ABAs overcome the limits of "flat" ABAs, which allow the inferred assumptions to conflict. However, like ASPIC+, the non-flat ABAs ignore the n-ary conflicts case. *Contrapositive* ABAs (Jesse Heyninck, 2020) and its collective attack version (Arieli & Heyninck, 2024), which use *contrapositive propositional logic*, propose extended forms for 'flat' and 'non-flat' ABAs. While (Arieli & Heyninck, 2024) mainly focuses on representation (which can be simulated in our setting, see after Definition 5 in Section 3.1), we extend our study to proof procedures in AFs with collective attacks.

Argumentation offers dialogue models and dispute trees to determine and explain the acceptance of propositions for classical logic (Castagna, 2021), for Datalog[±] (Arioua, Buche, & Croitoru, 2017; Arioua, Tamani, Croitoru, & Buche, 2014; Arioua & Croitoru, 2016; Arioua et al., 2017), for logic programming/ default logic (Thang, Dung, & Hung, 2012; Fan & Toni, 2014), and for defeasible logic (Prakken, 2005). However, the models have limitations. In (Arioua et al., 2017, 2014), the dialogue models take place between a domain expert but are only applied to a specific domain (agronomy). In (Arioua & Croitoru, 2016; Arioua et al., 2017; Prakken, 2005; Castagna, 2021), persuasion dialogues generate the abstract dispute trees defined abstractly that include arguments and attacks and ignore the internal structure of the argument. These works lack exhaustive explanations, making them insufficient for understanding inference steps and argument structures. The works in (Dung, Kowalski, & Toni, 2006; Dung, Mancarella, & Toni, 2007) provide dialectical proof procedures, while the works in (Fan & Toni, 2014; Thang et al., 2012) offer dialogue games (as a distributed mechanism) for "flat" ABAs to determine sentence acceptance under (grounded/ admissible/ ideal) semantics. Although the works in (Fan & Toni, 2014; Thang et al., 2012) are similar to our idea of using dialogue games and trees, these approaches do not generalize to n-ary conflicts. The work proposes discussion games and dispute trees tailored to AFs and ABAs with collective attacks, and shows that they correspond to credulous acceptance w.r.t. preferred semantics (Buraglio, Dvorak, König, & Ulbricht, 2024). In contrast, we extend the study to sceptical and grounded acceptance, and demonstrate that our approach can be applied to other rule-based systems such as ASPIC, logic-based argumentation and DeLP - as mentioned in the future work of (Buraglio et al., 2024).

The existing studies are mostly restricted to (1) specific logic or have limitations in representation aspects, and (2) AFs with binary conflicts. This paper addresses the limitations by introducing a **proof-oriented (logical) argumentation framework with collective attacks** (P-SAF) that increases the expressive power of the argumentation frameworks. The idea is to use **abstract logic** to generalize monotonic and non-monotonic logics involving reasoning with maximal consistent subsets, and showing how any such logic can be translated to P-SAFs and how P-SAFs can capture cases in which n-ary conflicts may arise. P-SAFs exhibit several benefits, notably providing **explanatory dialogue models** and **dialogue trees** to compute and explain the acceptance of a given query for reasoning with conflicting information.

To see how turning to P-SAFs provides more exhaustive explanations, consider the following simple example.

Example 1. Consider inconsistent knowledge about a university domain, in which we know that: lecturers (**Le**) and researchers (**Re**) are employers (**Em**); full professors (**FP**) are researchers; everyone who is a teaching assistant of (**taOf**) an undergraduate course (**UC**) is a teaching assistant (**TA**); everyone who teaches a course is a lecturer and everyone who teaches a graduate course (**GC**) is a full professor. However, teaching assistants can be neither researchers nor lecturers, which leads to inconsistency. We also know that an individual Victor apparently is or was a teaching assistant of the *KD* course (**taOf**(*v*,*KD*)), and the *KD* course is an undergraduate course (**UC**(*KD*)). Victor teaches the *KD* course (**te**(*v*,*KD*)) or the *KR* course (**te**(*v*,*KR*)), where the *KR* course is a graduate course (**GC**(*KR*)). The KB \mathcal{K}_1 is modelled as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_1 &= \{\mathbf{taOf}(v, KD), \mathbf{te}(v, KD), \mathbf{UC}(KD), \mathbf{te}(v, KR), \mathbf{GC}(KR)\} \\ \mathcal{R}_1 &= \{r_1 : \mathbf{Le}(x) \rightarrow \mathbf{Em}(x), r_2 : \mathbf{Re}(x) \rightarrow \mathbf{Em}(x), \\ &\quad r_3 : \mathbf{FP}(x) \rightarrow \mathbf{Re}(x), r_4 : \mathbf{taOf}(x, y) \wedge \mathbf{UC}(y) \rightarrow \mathbf{TA}(x), \\ &\quad r_5 : \mathbf{te}(x, y) \rightarrow \mathbf{Le}(x), r_6 : \mathbf{te}(x, y) \wedge \mathbf{GC}(y) \rightarrow \mathbf{FP}(x)\} \\ \mathcal{C}_1 &= \{c_1 : \mathbf{TA}(x) \wedge \mathbf{Re}(x) \rightarrow \perp, c_2 : \mathbf{Le}(x) \wedge \mathbf{TA}(x) \rightarrow \perp\} \end{aligned}$$

When a user asks "Is Victor a researcher?", the answer will be "Yes, but Victor is possibly a researcher". The current method (Lukasiewicz, Malizia, & Molinaro, 2020, 2022; Bienvenu, Bourgaux, & Goasdoué, 2019) will provide a set-based explanation consisting of (1) the cause (also called a minimal set of facts) $\{\mathbf{te}(v, KR), \mathbf{GC}(KR)\}$ entailing the answer (explaining why the answer is accepted) and (2) the conflict $\{\mathbf{taOf}(v, KD), \mathbf{UC}(KD)\}$ being inconsistent with every cause (explaining why the answer cannot be accepted). The cause, though, does not show a series of reasoning steps to reach $\mathbf{Re}(v)$ from the justification $\{\mathbf{te}(v, KR), \mathbf{GC}(KR)\}$. The conflict still lacks all relevant information to explain this result. Indeed, in the KB, the fact $\mathbf{te}(v, KD)$ deducing $\mathbf{Le}(v)$ makes the conflict $\{\mathbf{taOf}(v, KD), \mathbf{UC}(KD)\}$ deducing $\mathbf{TA}(v)$ uncertain, due to the constraint that lecturers cannot be teaching assistants. Thus, using the conflict in the explanation is insufficient to assert the non-acceptance of the answer. It remains unclear why the answer is possible. Instead, $\mathbf{te}(v, KD)$ deducing $\mathbf{Le}(v)$ should be included in the explanation. Without knowing the relevant information, it is impossible for the user - especially non-experts in logic - to understand why this is the case.

However, using the argumentation approach will provide a dialogical explanation that is more informative and intuitive. The idea involves a dialogue between a proponent and an opponent, where they exchange logical formulas to a dispute agree. The proponent aims to prove that the argument in question is acceptable, while the opponent exhaustively challenges the proponent's moves. The dialogue where the proponent wins represents a proof that the argument in question is accepted. The dialogue whose graphical representation is shown in Figure 3 proceeds as follows:

1. Suppose that the proponent wants to defend their claim $\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$. They can do so by putting forward an argument, say A_1 , supported by facts $\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})$ and $\text{GC}(\text{KR})$:

$A_1 : \text{Re}(\mathbf{v})(\text{by } r_3)$
 $\text{FP}(\mathbf{v})(\text{by } r_6)$
 $\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR}), \text{GC}(\text{KR})(\text{by facts})$

Proponent: I believe that \mathbf{v} is a researcher because he is a full professor; and given the fact that he teaches the KR course and KR is a graduate course.

2. The opponent challenges the proponent's argument by attacking the claim $\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$ with an argument $\text{TA}(\mathbf{v})$, say A_2 , supported by facts $\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})$ and $\text{UC}(\text{KD})$:

$A_2 : \text{TA}(\mathbf{v})(\text{by } r_4)$
 $\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD}), \text{UC}(\text{KD})(\text{by facts})$

Opponent: \mathbf{v} is not possibly a researcher because \mathbf{v} is a TA given the fact that he is a TA of the KD course and KD is an undergraduate course.

3. To argue that the opponent's attack is not possible - and to further defend the initial claim $\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$ - the proponent can counter the opponent's argument by providing additional evidence $\text{Le}(\mathbf{v})$ supported by a fact $\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})$:

$A_3 : \text{Le}(\mathbf{v})(\text{by } r_5)$
 $\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})(\text{by facts})$

Proponent: \mathbf{v} is not possibly a TA because \mathbf{v} is certainly a lecturer given the fact that he teaches the KD course.

4. The opponent concedes $\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$ since it has no argument to argue the proponent.

Opponent: I concede that \mathbf{v} is a researcher because I have no argument to argue that \mathbf{v} is neither a lecturer nor researcher.

The proponent's belief $\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$ is defended successfully, namely, $\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$ that is justified by facts $\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR}), \text{GC}(\text{KR})\}$ that be extended to be the defending set $\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR}), \text{GC}(\text{KR}), \text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})\}$ that can counter-attack every attack.

By the same line of reasoning, the opponent can similarly defend their belief in the contrary statement $\text{TA}(\mathbf{v})$ based on the defending set $\{\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD}), \text{UC}(\text{KD})\}$. Because different agents can hold contrary claims, the acceptance semantics of the answer can be considered credulous rather than sceptical. In other words, the answer is deemed possible rather than plausible. Thus, the derived system can conclude that \mathbf{v} is possibly a researcher.

It can easily be noted that the set-based explanations present the necessary premises of an entailment and, as such, do not articulate the (often non-obvious) reasoning that connects those premises with the conclusion nor track conflicts. Another line of work proposes *proof-based explanations*, which offer graphical representations to help users better understand the reasoning process (Alrabbaa, Borgwardt, Koopmann, & Kovtunova, 2022). Unfortunately,

the research in this area generally focuses on reasoning in *consistent* KBs. Overall, the limit of the above approaches is that they do not track contradictions, whereas argumentation frameworks can address this shortcoming. Indeed, as illustrated in the motivating example, argumentation can support understanding of the intermediate steps of a logical reasoning process in the presence of inconsistencies. As a result, the P-SAF offers a more intuitive and exhaustive explanation compared to set- or proof-based explanations. Beside this evident advantage, no previous work has focused on implementing dialogue games and dialogue trees tailored for structured argumentation formalisms with collective attacks. The present work aims at bridging this gap. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a proof-oriented (logical) argumentation framework with collective attacks to enhance the expressive power of the argumentation framework, and we link reasoning with P-SAFs to logical reasoning with inconsistencies in Section 3.
- In Section 4 and 5, we generalize explanatory dialogue models and dialogue trees tailored for P-SAFs to compute and exhaustively explain the *credulous*, *grounded* and *sceptical* acceptances.
- We study computational aspects of the explanatory dialogue model in Section 6.

2. Preliminaries

The main aim of this paper is to explain logical reasoning in (inconsistent) KBs through argumentation. To motivate our work, we review existing argumentation approaches. However, many logic in argumentation systems, like ABA or ASPIC systems, do not always impose certain axioms, such as the absurdity axiom. Frameworks based on Tarski abstract logic, where the consequence operator is defined by means of "models", cannot allow users to understand reasoning progresses better, as inference rule steps are implicit (Amgoud & Besnard, 2009). These motivate a slight generalization of consequence operators in a proof-theoretic manner, inspired by (Bloom, 1975), with minimal properties.

Most of our discussion applies to abstract logics (monotonic and non-monotonic) which slightly generalize Tarski abstract logic. We assume the reader to be familiar with the terminology of logic. Let \mathcal{L} be a set of *well-formed formulas*, or simply *formulas*, and X be an arbitrary set of formulas in \mathcal{L} . With the help of *inference rules*, new formulas are derived from X ; these formulas are called *logical consequences* of X ; a *consequence operator* (called *closure operator*) returns the logical consequences of a set of formulas.

Definition 1. We define a map $\text{CN} : 2^{\mathcal{L}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}}$ such that $\overline{\text{CN}}(X) = \bigcup_{n \geq 0} \text{CN}^n(X)$ satisfies the axioms:

- (A_1) **Expansion** $X \subseteq \overline{\text{CN}}(X)$.
- (A_2) **Idempotence** $\overline{\text{CN}}(\overline{\text{CN}}(X)) = \overline{\text{CN}}(X)$.

In general, a map $2^{\mathcal{L}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}}$ satisfying these axioms $A_1 - A_2$ is called a *consequence operator*. Other properties that consequence operators might have, but that we do not require in this paper, are

- (A₃) **Finiteness** $\overline{\text{CN}}(X) \subseteq \bigcup\{\overline{\text{CN}}(Y) \mid Y \subseteq X, Y \text{ finite}\}$.
- (A₄) **Coherence** $\overline{\text{CN}}(\emptyset) \neq \mathcal{L}$.
- (A₅) **Absurdity** $\overline{\text{CN}}(\{x\}) = \mathcal{L}$ for some x in the language \mathcal{L} .

Note that finiteness is essential for practical reasoning and is satisfied by any logic that has a decent proof system.

In what follows, we provide a definition of abstract logic.

Definition 2. An abstract logic includes a pair \mathcal{L} and a consequence operator CN .

Different logics have consequence operators with various properties that can satisfy certain axioms. For instance, the class of Tarskian logics, such as classical logic, is defined by a consequence operator satisfying $A_1 - A_5$ while the one of defeasible logic satisfies $A_1 - A_3$.

Example 2. An inference rule r in first-order logic is of the form $\frac{p_1, \dots, p_n}{c}$ where its conclusion is c and the premises are p_1, \dots, p_n . c is called a direct consequence of p_1, \dots, p_n by virtue of r . If we define $\text{CN}(X)$ as the set of direct consequences of $X \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, then $\overline{\text{CN}}$ coincides with $\overline{\text{CN}}(X) = \{\alpha \in \mathcal{L} \mid X \vdash \alpha\}$ and satisfies the axioms $A_1 - A_5$.

A knowledge base (KB) is any subset \mathcal{K} of \mathcal{L} . Facts are assertions about the world, represented as formulas within a KB. Fix an abstract logic (\mathcal{L}, CN) and a set of formulas $X \subseteq \mathcal{K}$. We say that:

- X is consistent wrt (\mathcal{L}, CN) iff $\overline{\text{CN}}(X) \neq \mathcal{L}$. It is inconsistent otherwise; \mathcal{K} may be inconsistent.
- X is a minimal conflict of \mathcal{K} if $X' \subsetneq X$ implies X' is consistent.

Reasoning in inconsistent KBs $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ amounts to:

1. Constructing maximal consistent subsets,
2. Applying classical entailment mechanism on a choice of the maximal consistent subsets.

Motivated by this idea, we give the following definition.

Definition 3. Let \mathcal{K} be a KB and $X \subseteq \mathcal{K}$ be a set of formulas. X is a maximal (for set-inclusion) consistent subset (MCS) of \mathcal{K} iff

- X is consistent,
- there is no X' of \mathcal{K} such that $X \subset X'$ and X' is consistent.

We denote the set of all maximal consistent subsets by $\text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$.

Inconsistency-tolerant semantics allow us to determine different types of entailments.

Definition 4. Let \mathcal{K} be a KB. A formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ is entailed in

- some maximal consistent subset *iff for some* $\Delta \in \text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\Delta)$;
- *the intersection of all maximal consistent subsets iff for* $\Psi = \bigcap\{\Delta \mid \Delta \in \text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})\}$, $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\Psi)$;
- all maximal consistent subsets *iff for all* $\Delta \in \text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\Delta)$.

Informally, *some maximal consistent subset semantics* refers to **possible answers**, *all maximal consistent subsets semantics* to **plausible answers**, and the *intersection of all maximal consistent subsets semantics* to **surest answers**.

In the following subsections, we illustrate the generality of the above definitions by providing instantiations for propositional logic, defeasible logic, Datalog[±]. Table 1 summarizes properties holding for consequence operators of the instantiations.

Axioms	CN _p	CN _d	CN _{co}	CN _{da}
A ₁	×	×	×	×
A ₂	×	×	×	×
A ₃	×	×	×	
A ₄	×			
A ₅	×			

Table 1: Properties of consequence operators of the instantiations

2.1 Propositional Logic

Let A be a set of propositional atoms. Any atoms $a \in A$ is a well-formed formula wrt. A . If ϕ and α are well-formed formulas wrt. A then $\neg\phi$, $\phi \wedge \alpha$, $\phi \vee \alpha$ are well-formulas wrt. A (we also assume that the usual abbreviations \supset , \leftrightarrow are defined accordingly). Then a logic language \mathcal{L}_p for propositional logic is the set of well-formed formulas wrt. A .

Let $\text{CN}_p : 2^{\mathcal{L}_p} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}_p}$ be defined as follows: for $X \subseteq \mathcal{L}_p$, an element $x \in \mathcal{L}_p$ satisfies $x \in \text{CN}_p(X)$ iff there are $y_1, \dots, y_j \in X$ such that x can be obtained from y_1, \dots, y_j by the application of a single inference rule of the form $\frac{y}{x}$. Define $\overline{\text{CN}}_p(X) = \bigcup_{n \geq 0} \text{CN}_p^n(X)$. Since propositional logic is coherent and complete, then $x \in \overline{\text{CN}}_p(X) = \{x \mid X \models x\}$ where \models is the entailment relation, i.e., $\phi \models \alpha$ if all models of ϕ are models of α in the propositional semantics. In particular, $\overline{\text{CN}}_p$ is a consequence operator satisfying $A_1 - A_5$. Now the propositional logic can be defined as $(\mathcal{L}_p, \text{CN}_p)$.

Example 3. Consider the propositional atoms $A_1 = \{x, y\}$ and the knowledge base $\mathcal{K}_1 = \{x, y, x \supset \neg y\} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_p$.

Consider a set $\{x, x \supset \neg y\} \subseteq \mathcal{K}_1$. If the inference rule (modus ponens) $\frac{A, A \supset B}{B}$ is applied to this set, then $\text{CN}_p(\{x, x \supset \neg y\}) = \{x, x \supset \neg y, \neg y\}$. Then $\overline{\text{CN}}_p(\mathcal{K}_1) = \{x, y, x \supset \neg y, \neg y, x \wedge y, \dots\}$.

Observe that, by definition, the logic $(\mathcal{L}_p, \text{CN}_p)$ properly models propositional logics.

The KB admits MCSs: $\{x, x \supset \neg y\}$, $\{y, x \supset \neg y\}$, $\{x, y\}$.

2.2 Defeasible Logic

This section presents a form of *defeasible logic*, as used in defeasible logic programming (García & Simari, 2014), assumption-based argumentation (ABA) (Dung et al., 2009), and ASPIC/ASPIC+ systems (Prakken & Vreeswijk, 2002; Modgil & Prakken, 2014). Two representations of defeasible logic are discussed in the following.

In the first proposal, a rule has the form of $x_1, \dots, x_i \rightarrow_s x_{i+1}$ ($x_1, \dots, x_i \rightarrow_d x_{i+1}$) where x_1, \dots, x_i, x_{i+1} are literals and \rightarrow_s (denotes strict rules) and \rightarrow_d (denotes defeasible rules) are implication symbols. The language for defeasible logic \mathcal{L}_d includes a set of (strict and defeasible) rules and a set of literals.

Define $\text{CN}_d : 2^{\mathcal{L}_d} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}_d}$ as follows: for $X \subseteq \mathcal{L}_d$, a formula $x \in \mathcal{L}_d$ satisfies $x \in \text{CN}_d(X)$ iff at least of the following properties is true:

1. x is a literal in X ,
2. there is $(y_1, \dots, y_j) \rightarrow_s x \in X$, or $(y_1, \dots, y_j) \rightarrow_d x \in X$ st. $\{y_1, \dots, y_j\} \subseteq X$.

Define $\overline{\text{CN}}_d(X) = \bigcup_{n \geq 0} \text{CN}_d^n(X)$ ¹. Following (Amgoud, 2012), $\overline{\text{CN}}_d$ satisfies $A_1 - A_3$. Then the defeasible logic is defined as $(\mathcal{L}_d, \text{CN}_d)$.

Example 4. Consider the KB $\mathcal{K}_2 = \{x, x \rightarrow_s y, t \rightarrow_d z\} \subseteq \mathcal{L}_d$. $\overline{\text{CN}}_d(\mathcal{K}_2) = \{x, y\}$ where the sequence of literals in the derivation is x, y . Obviously the logic $(\mathcal{L}_d, \text{CN}_d)$ properly models defeasible logic for the first proposal. We have that \mathcal{K}_2 is a MCS.

In the above proposal, the use of defeasible logic in argumentation systems has been criticized for violating the postulates that they proposed for acceptable argumentation (Camínada & Amgoud, 2007). One possible solution is to introduce *contraposition* into the reasoning of the underlying logic, as discussed below.

Consider \mathcal{L}_{co} containing a set of literal and a set of strict (resp., defeasible) rules \mathcal{R}_s (resp., \mathcal{R}_d). For this case, inference rules are parts of a consequence operator. For $\Delta \subseteq \mathcal{L}_{co}$, $\text{Contrapositives}(\Delta)$ is the set of contrapositives formed from the rules in Δ . A strict rule s is a contraposition of the rule $\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n \rightarrow_s \alpha \in \mathcal{R}_s$ iff $s = \phi_1, \dots, \phi_{i-1}, \neg\alpha, \phi_{i+1}, \dots, \phi_n \rightarrow_s \neg\phi_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Define $\text{CN}_{co} : 2^{\mathcal{L}_{co}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}_{co}}$ as follows: for a set of literals $X \subseteq \mathcal{L}_{co}$, a formula $x \in \mathcal{L}_{co}$ satisfies $x \in \text{CN}_{co}(X)$ iff at least of the following properties is true:

1. One can describe $\overline{\text{CN}}_d$ explicitly. We have $x \in \overline{\text{CN}}_d(X)$ iff there exists a finite *sequence* of literals x_1, \dots, x_n such that x is x_n , and for each $x_i \in \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, there is $y_1, \dots, y_j \rightarrow_s x_i \in X$, or $y_1, \dots, y_j \rightarrow_d x_i \in X$, such that $\{y_1, \dots, y_j\} \subseteq \{x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}\}$, or x_i is a literal in X .

Note that if $x \in \text{CN}_d^n(X)$, the above sequence x_1, \dots, x_n might have length $m \neq n$: intuitively n is the depth of the tree-derivation while m is the number of nodes.

Remark 1. For ASPIC/ASPIC+ systems (Prakken & Vreeswijk, 2002; Modgil & Prakken, 2014), Prakken claimed that strict and defeasible rules can be considered in two ways: (1) they encode information of the knowledge base, in which case they are part of the logical language \mathcal{L}_d , (2) they represent inference rules, in which case they are part of the consequence operator. These ways can be encoded by consequence operators as in (Amgoud, 2012). Our definition of $\overline{\text{CN}}_d$ can align with the later interpretation as done in (Amgoud, 2012). In particular, if we consider X being a set of literals of \mathcal{L}_d instead of being a set of literals and rules as above, the definitions of CN_d and $\overline{\text{CN}}_d$ still hold for this case. Thus, the defeasible logic of ASPIC/ASPIC+ can be represented by the logic $(\mathcal{L}_d, \text{CN}_d)$ in our settings.

1. x is a literal in X ,
2. there is $(y_1, \dots, y_j) \rightarrow_s x \in \mathcal{R}_s \cup \text{Contrapositives}(\mathcal{R}_s)$, or $(y_1, \dots, y_j) \rightarrow_d x \in \mathcal{R}_d \cup \text{Contrapositives}(\mathcal{R}_d)$ such that $\{y_1, \dots, y_j\} \subseteq X$.

Define $\overline{\text{CN}}_{co}(X) = \bigcup_{n \geq 0} \text{CN}_{co}^n(X)$ ². $\overline{\text{CN}}_{co}$ satisfies $A_1 - A_3$. Then the defeasible logic can also be defined as $(\mathcal{L}_{co}, \text{CN}_{co})$.

Example 5. Consider $\mathcal{K}_3 = \{q, \neg r, p \wedge q \rightarrow_d r, \neg p \rightarrow_s u\}$. We have $\text{Contrapositives}(\mathcal{K}_3) = \{\neg r \wedge q \rightarrow_d \neg p, \neg r \wedge p \rightarrow_d \neg q, \neg u \rightarrow_s p\}$. Then $\overline{\text{CN}}_{co}(\mathcal{K}_3) = \{q, \neg r, \neg p, u\}$ where the sequence of literals in the derivation is $q, \neg r, \neg p, u$. Obviously the logic $(\mathcal{L}_{co}, \text{CN}_{co})$ properly models defeasible logic for the second proposal.

The KB admits MCSs: $\{q, \neg r, \neg p \rightarrow_s u\}$ and $\{q, p \wedge q \rightarrow_d r, \neg p \rightarrow_s u\}$.

2.3 Datalog[±]

We consider Datalog[±] (Calì, Gottlob, & Lukasiewicz, 2012), and shall use it to illustrate our demonstrations through the paper.

Assume that a set \mathbf{N}_t of *terms* which contain variables, constants and function terms. An atom is of the form $P(\vec{t})$, with P a predicate name and \vec{t} a vector of terms, which is *ground* if it contains no variables. A *database* is a finite set of ground atoms (called *facts*). A *tuple-generating dependency* (TGD) σ is a first-order formula of the form $\forall \vec{x} \forall \vec{y} \phi(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) \rightarrow \exists \vec{z} \psi(\vec{x}, \vec{z})$, where $\phi(\vec{x}, \vec{y})$ and $\psi(\vec{x}, \vec{z})$ are non-empty conjunctions of atoms. We leave out the universal quantification, and refer to $\phi(\vec{x}, \vec{y})$ and $\psi(\vec{x}, \vec{z})$ as the *body* and *head* of σ . A *negative constraint* (NC) δ is a rule of the form $\forall \vec{x} \phi(\vec{x}) \rightarrow \perp$ where $\phi(\vec{x})$ is a conjunction of atoms. A language for Datalog[±] \mathcal{L}_{da} includes a set of facts and a set of TGDs and NCs. A knowledge base \mathcal{K} of \mathcal{L}_{da} is now a tuple $(\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C})$ where a database \mathcal{F} , a set \mathcal{R} of TGDs and a set \mathcal{C} of NCs.

Such TGDs and NCs are treated as inference rules that form part of a consequence operator. Define $\text{CN}_{da} : 2^{\mathcal{L}_{da}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{L}_{da}}$ as follows: Let X be a set of facts of \mathcal{F} , an element $x \in \mathcal{L}_{da}$ satisfies $x \in \text{CN}_{da}(X)$ iff there are $y_1, \dots, y_j \in X$ s.t. x can be obtained from y_1, \dots, y_j by the application of a single inference rule. Define $\overline{\text{CN}}_{da}(X) = \bigcup_{n \geq 0} \text{CN}_{da}^n(X)$. We say that $x \in \overline{\text{CN}}_{da}(X) = \{x \mid X \models x\}$, where \models is the entailment of first-order formulas, i.e., $X \models x$ holds iff every model of all elements in X is also a model of x . In particular, $\overline{\text{CN}}_{da}$ satisfies the properties A_1, A_2 ³ Then the Datalog[±] logic can be defined as $(\mathcal{L}_{da}, \text{CN}_{da})$.

Example 6 (Continue Example 1). Recall $\mathcal{K}_1 = (\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{C}_1) \subseteq \mathcal{L}_{da}$.

2. One can represent $\overline{\text{CN}}_{co}$ as follows: $x \in \overline{\text{CN}}_{co}(X)$ iff there exists a *sequence* of literals x_1, \dots, x_n such that x is x_n , and for each $x_i \in \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$,
 - there is $y_1, \dots, y_j \rightarrow_s x_i \in \mathcal{R}_s \cup \text{Contrapositives}(\mathcal{R}_s)$, or $y_1, \dots, y_j \rightarrow_d x_i \in \mathcal{R}_d \cup \text{Contrapositives}(\mathcal{R}_d)$, such that $\{y_1, \dots, y_j\} \subseteq \{x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}\}$,
 - or x_i is a literal in X .
3. Note that the finiteness property (A_3) still holds for some fragments of Datalog[±], such as *guarded*, *weakly guarded* Datalog[±].

Consider a set of facts $F = \{\mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR})\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}_1$. If the rule $r_5 : \mathbf{te}(x, y) \rightarrow \mathbf{Le}(x) \in \mathcal{R}_1$ is applicable⁴ to this set, then $\mathbf{CN}_{da}(F) = \{\mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{Le}(\mathbf{v})\}$. Then $\overline{\mathbf{CN}}_{da}(F) = \{\mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{Le}(\mathbf{v}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{FP}(\mathbf{v})\}$ (by the application of rules r_5, r_6).

Observe that, by definition, the logic $(\mathcal{L}_{da}, \mathbf{CN}_{da})$ properly models Datalog^\pm .

The KB admits MSCs of \mathcal{F}_1 (called repairs in Datalog^\pm):

$$\mathcal{B}_1 = \{\mathbf{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR})\},$$

$$\mathcal{B}_2 = \{\mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{UC}(\mathbf{KD})\},$$

$$\mathcal{B}_3 = \{\mathbf{UC}(\mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR})\}.$$

Consider $q_1 = \mathbf{Re}(\mathbf{v})$. We have that \mathbf{v} is a possible answer for q_1 since q_1 is entailed in some repairs, such as $\mathcal{B}_1, \mathcal{B}_2$.

3. Proof-oriented (Logical) Argumentations

In this section, we present *proof-oriented (logical) argumentations* (P-SAFs) and their ingredients. We show the close relations of reasoning with P-SAFs to reasoning with MCSs.

3.1 Arguments, Collective Attacks and Proof-oriented Argumentations

Logical arguments (*arguments* for short) built from a KB may be defined in different ways. For instance, arguments are represented by the notion of *sequents* (Arieli & Straßer, 2019), *proof* (Schulz & Toni, 2016; Dung et al., 2009), or a pair of (Γ, ψ) where Γ is the *support*, or *premises*, or *assumptions* of the argument, and ψ is the *claim*, or *conclusion*, of the argument (Ho et al., 2022; Arioua et al., 2017). To improve explanations in terms of representation and understanding, we adopt the form of *proof* to represent arguments. The proof is in the form of a tree.

Definition 5 (Arguments). *A formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ is tree-derivable from a set of fact-premises $H \subseteq \mathcal{K}$ if there is a tree such that*

- the root holds ϕ ;
- H is the set of formulas held by leaves;
- for every inner node N , if N holds the formula β_0 , then its successors hold n formulas β_1, \dots, β_n such that $\beta_0 \in \mathbf{CN}(\{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n\})$.

If such a tree exists (it might not be unique), we call $A : H \Rightarrow \phi$ an argument with the support set $\mathbf{Sup}(A) = H$ and the conclusion $\mathbf{Con}(A) = \phi$. We denote the set of arguments induced from \mathcal{K} by $\mathbf{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}$.

Remark 2. By Definition 5 it follows that $H \Rightarrow \phi$ is an argument iff $\phi \in \overline{\mathbf{CN}}(H)$.

Note that there can be several derivation trees (with the same root and leaves) (Definition 5) that yield arguments with the same conclusion and support set. We assume

4. Consider a set $I \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ and a TGD σ of the form $\phi(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) \rightarrow \exists z \varphi(\vec{x}, \vec{z})$. We say that σ is *applicable* w.r.t. I if there exists a homomorphism h from $\phi(\vec{x}, \vec{y})$ to I .

that these trees represent the same arguments; otherwise, we could have infinitely many arguments with the same support set and conclusion. Our notion of a P-SAF argument (Definition 5) is in line with the notation in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024). However, for the purpose of the P-SAF semantics, it does not matter whether one defines arguments as derivation trees or as pairs of supports and conclusions, since the semantics are characterized by considering this information only. To keep our framework as general as possible, we do not consider the minimality and consistency restrictions for our argument definition ⁵.

Note that multiple derivation trees (Definition 5) with the same root and leaves can yield arguments with identical conclusions and support sets. We treat such trees as representing the same argument; otherwise, infinitely many arguments could share the same support and conclusion. Our notion of a P-SAF argument (Definition 5) follows the notation in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024). For the purpose of P-SAF semantics, it is irrelevant whether arguments are defined as derivation trees or as support–conclusion pairs, since the semantics rely only on this information. Formally, arguments viewed as support–conclusion pairs correspond to equivalence classes of derivation trees. To keep the framework general, we do not impose minimality or consistency constraints on our definition of arguments.

Intuitively, a tree represents a possible derivation of the formula at its root and the fact-premise made at its leaves. The leaves of the tree, constituting the fact-premise, belong to $H = \text{CN}^0(H)$. If a node β has children nodes $\beta_{a_1} \in \text{CN}^{i_1}(H), \dots, \beta_{a_k} \in \text{CN}^{i_k}(H)$, then $\beta \in \text{CN}^{i+1}(X)$ where $i = \max\{i_1, \dots, i_k\}$ because by the extension property $\text{CN}^{i_1}(H), \dots, \text{CN}^{i_k}(H) \subseteq \text{CN}^i(H)$. The root ϕ , constituting the conclusion, belongs to $\text{CN}^n(H)$, where n is the longest path from leaf to root. Note that, if $\beta \in \text{CN}^i(H)$, then also $\beta \in \text{CN}^{i+1}(H), \beta \in \text{CN}^{i+2}(H), \dots$. The idea is to have i in $\text{CN}^i(H)$ as small as possible (we don’t want to argue longer than necessary).

As shown in examples of (Yun et al., 2020; Amgoud, 2012; Arieli & Heyninck, 2024), binary attacks, used in the literature (Arieli & Straßer, 2019; Arioua et al., 2017; Ho et al., 2022; Zhang & Lin, 2013; Castagna, 2021), are not enough expressive to capture cases in which n-ary conflicts may arise. To overcome this limit, some argumentation frameworks introduced the notion of *collective attacks* to better capture non-binary conflicts ⁶, and so improve the decision making process in various conflicting situations. To ensure the generality of our framework, we introduce collective attacks.

Definition 6 (Collective Attacks). *Let $A : \Gamma \Rightarrow \alpha$ be an argument and $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}$ be a set of arguments such that $\bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{X}} \text{Sup}(X)$ is consistent. We say that*

-
5. Some proposals for logic-based argumentation stipulate additionally that the argument’s support is consistent and/or that none of its subsets entails the argument’s conclusion (see (Hunter, 2010)). However, such restrictions, namely, the minimality and consistency of an argument’s support, are not substantial (although required for some specific logics). In some proposals, the requirement that the support of an argument is consistent may be irrelevant for some logics, especially when consistency is defined by satisfiability. For instance, in Priest’s three-valued logic (Priest, 1989) or Belnap’s four-valued logic (Belnap, 1977), every set of formulas in the language of $\{\neg, \vee, \wedge\}$ is satisfiable. In frameworks in which the supports of arguments are represented only by literals (atomic formulas or their negation), arguments like $A = \{a, b\} \Rightarrow a \vee b$ are excluded since their supports are not minimal, although one may consider $\{a, b\}$ a stronger support for $a \vee b$ than, say, $\{a\}$, since the set $\{a, b\}$ logically implies every minimal support of $a \vee b$. To keep our framework as general as possible, we do not consider the extra restrictions for our definition of arguments (See (Hunter, 2010; Arieli & Straßer, 2019) for further justifications of this choice)
 6. For the case of *non-binary conflicts*, we do not assume that every conflict has only two facts.

- \mathcal{X} undercut-attacks A iff there is $\Gamma' \subseteq \Gamma$ s.t $\bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{X}} \{\text{Con}(X)\} \cup \Gamma'$ is inconsistent.
- \mathcal{X} rebuttal-attacks A iff $\bigcup_{X \in \mathcal{X}} \{\text{Con}(X)\} \cup \{\alpha\}$ is inconsistent.

We can say that \mathcal{X} attacks A for short. We use $\text{Att}_{\mathcal{K}} \subseteq 2^{\text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}} \times \text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}$ to denote the set of attacks induced from \mathcal{K} .

Note that deductive argumentation can capture n-ary conflicts. However, the authors in (Yun et al., 2020, 2018) argued that the argumentation framework using Datalog[±], an instance of deductive argumentation, may generate a large number of arguments and attacks when using the definition of deductive arguments, as in (Arioua et al., 2017). To address this problem, some redundant arguments are dropped, as discussed in (Yun et al., 2018), or arguments are re-defined as those in ASPIC+, as seen in (Yun et al., 2020). Then the attack relation must be redesigned to preserve all conflicts. In particular, n-ary attacks are allowed where arguments can jointly attack an argument. We will show this issue in the following example.

Example 7. Consider $\mathcal{K}_2 = (\mathcal{F}_2, \mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{C}_2)$ where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_2 &= \emptyset, \\ \mathcal{C}_2 &= \{A(x) \wedge B(x) \wedge C(x) \rightarrow \perp\}, \\ \mathcal{F}_2 &= \{A(a), B(a), C(a)\}. \end{aligned}$$

The deductive argumentation approach (Arioua et al., 2017) uses six arguments

$$\begin{aligned} C_2 : (\{B(a)\}, B(a)), C_3 : (\{C(a)\}, C(a)), C_4 : (\{A(a), B(a)\}, A(a) \wedge B(a)), \\ C_1 : (\{A(a)\}, A(a)), C_5 : (\{A(a), C(a)\}, A(a) \wedge C(a)), C_6 : (\{B(a), C(a)\}, B(a) \wedge C(a)) \end{aligned}$$

to obtains the preferred sets: $\{C_1, C_2, C_4\}$, $\{C_1, C_3, C_5\}$, $\{C_2, C_3, C_6\}$.

In contrast, our approach uses three arguments $B_1 : \{A(a)\} \Rightarrow A(a)$, $B_2 : \{B(a)\} \Rightarrow B(a)$, $B_3 : \{C(a)\} \Rightarrow C(a)$ with collective attacks, such as $\{B_1, B_2\}$ attacks B_3 , etc., to obtain extensions $\{B_1, B_2\}$, $\{B_1, B_3\}$, $\{B_2, B_3\}$.

Remark 3. Note that the definition of collective attacks holds if we only consider ASPIC+ without preferences (Modgil & Prakken, 2014). We leave the case of preferences for future work.

We introduce P-SAFs as an instantiation of SAFs (Nielsen & Parsons, 2007).

Definition 7 (P-SAFs). Let \mathcal{K} be a KB based on the abstract logic (\mathcal{L}, CN) , the corresponding proof-oriented (logical) argumentation (P-SAF) $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$ is the pair $(\text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}, \text{Att}_{\mathcal{K}})$ where $\text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}$ is the set of arguments induced from \mathcal{K} and $\text{Att}_{\mathcal{K}}$ is the set of attacks.

3.2 Acceptability of P-SAFs and Relations to Reasoning with MSCs

We have presented the definition of P-SAFs. We next discuss reasoning in P-SAFs and a link between reasoning in P-SAFs and reasoning with MSCs.

Before continuing, we present notions used in reasoning in P-SAFs. Semantics of P-SAFs are now defined as the semantics in SAFs (Nielsen & Parsons, 2007). These semantics consist of *admissible*, *complete*, *stable*, *preferred* and *grounded semantics*.

Given a P-SAF $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K} = (\text{Arg}_\mathcal{K}, \text{Att}_\mathcal{K})$ and $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X} \subseteq \text{Arg}_\mathcal{K}$. \mathcal{S} attacks \mathcal{X} iff $\exists A \in \mathcal{X}$ s.t. \mathcal{S} attacks A . \mathcal{S} defends A if for each \mathcal{X} s.t. \mathcal{X} attacks A , some $\mathcal{S}' \subseteq \mathcal{S}$ attacks \mathcal{X} . An extension \mathcal{S} is called

- *conflict-free* if it does not attack itself;
- *admissible* (**adm**) if it is conflict-free and defends itself.
- *complete* (**cmp**) if it is admissible containing all arguments it defends.
- *preferred* (**prf**) if it is an inclusion-maximal admissible extension.
- *stable* (**stb**) if it is conflict-free and attacks every argument not in it.
- *grounded* (**grd**) if it is an inclusion-minimal complete extension.

Note that this implies that each grounded or preferred extension of a P-SAF is an admissible one, the grounded extension is contained in all other extensions.

We present notations that will be used throughout this paper.

Notation 1. Let \mathcal{X} be a set of facts of \mathcal{K} and $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \text{Arg}_\mathcal{K}$ be a set of arguments induced from \mathcal{K} . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Args}(\mathcal{X}) &= \{A \in \text{Arg}_\mathcal{K} \mid \text{Sup}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{X}\} \text{ are the set of arguments generated from } \mathcal{X}, \\ \text{Cons}(\mathcal{S}) &= \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{S}} \text{Con}(A) \text{ are the set of conclusions of arguments in } \mathcal{S}, \\ \text{Base}(\mathcal{S}) &= \bigcup_{A \in \mathcal{S}} \text{Sup}(A) \text{ are the set of supports of arguments in } \mathcal{S}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K})$ denote the set of all extensions of $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ under the semantics $\text{sem} \in \{\text{adm}, \text{stb}, \text{prf}, \text{grd}\}$. Let us define *acceptability* in P-SAFs.

Definition 8. Let $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ be the corresponding P-SAF of a KB \mathcal{K} and $\text{sem} \in \{\text{adm}, \text{stb}, \text{prf}\}$. A formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ is

- *credulously accepted under sem* iff for some $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$.
- *groundedly accepted under grd* iff for some $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}_{\text{grd}}(\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$.
- *sceptically accepted under sem* iff for all $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$.

Next, we show the relation to reasoning with maximal consistent subsets in inconsistent KBs. Proposition 1 shows a relation between extensions of P-SAFs and MSCs of KBs.

Proposition 1. Let $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ be the corresponding P-SAF of a KB \mathcal{K} . Then,

- the maximal consistent subset of \mathcal{K} coincides with the set of supports of arguments in the stable and preferred extension of $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$;
- the intersection of the maximal consistent subsets of \mathcal{K} coincides with the set of supports of arguments in the grounded extension of $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$.

Sketch. The idea of the proof is to show that every preferred extension is the set of supports of arguments generated from a MCS, that every such set of arguments is a stable extension, and that every stable extension is preferred. The proof of the second statement follows the lemma saying that if there are no rejected arguments under preferred semantics, then the grounded extension is equal to the intersection of all preferred extensions. By the proof of the first statement, the set of supports of arguments in every preferred extension is a maximal consistent subset. Thus, the second statement is proved. \square

Remark 4. *In general, the grounded extension is contained in the intersection of all maximal consistent subsets.*

The main result of this section, Theorem 1, which follows from Proposition 1 generalises results from previous works.

Theorem 1. *Let $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$ be the corresponding P-SAF of a KB \mathcal{K} , $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ a formula and $\text{sem} \in \{\text{stb}, \text{prf}\}$. Then, ϕ is entailed in*

- *all maximal consistent subsets iff ϕ is sceptically accepted under sem .*
- *some maximal consistent subset iff ϕ is credulously accepted under sem .*
- *the intersection of all maximal consistent subsets iff ϕ is groundedly accepted in grd .*

Proof. By Proposition 1, there exists a link between maximal consistent subsets of \mathcal{K} and extensions in $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$. Obviously, for every formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ and maximal consistent subset $\mathcal{M} \in \text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$, it is the case that $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\mathcal{M})$ iff ϕ is in the set of conclusions of the arguments generated from \mathcal{M} . The theorem is now proven as follows:

1. ϕ is in all maximal consistent subsets of \mathcal{K} iff for every maximal consistent subset \mathcal{M} in $\text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\mathcal{M})$ iff for every extension $\text{Args}(\mathcal{M})$ (the set of arguments generated from \mathcal{M}), $\phi \in \text{Cons}(\text{Args}(\mathcal{M}))$ iff ϕ is sceptically accepted.
2. ϕ is in some maximal consistent subset of \mathcal{K} iff for some maximal consistent subset \mathcal{M} in $\text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\mathcal{M})$ iff for some extension $\text{Args}(\mathcal{M})$ (the set of arguments generated from \mathcal{M}), $\phi \in \text{Cons}(\text{Args}(\mathcal{M}))$ iff ϕ is credulously accepted.
3. ϕ is in the intersection of maximal consistent subsets of \mathcal{K} iff for every $\mathcal{M}_i \in \text{MCS}(\mathcal{K})$, $\phi \in \overline{\text{CN}}(\bigcap \mathcal{M}_i)$ iff for every $\text{Args}(\mathcal{M}_i)$ (the set of arguments generated from \mathcal{M}_i), $\phi \in \text{Cons}(\bigcap \text{Args}(\mathcal{M}_i))$ iff ϕ is accepted under grounded semantics.

This ends the proof of Theorem 1. \square

Remark 5. *Since every admissible set (of arguments) is necessarily contained in a preferred set (see (Dung, 1995; Nielsen & Parsons, 2007)) and every preferred set is an admissible set by definition, we can use the results of Item 1 and 2 of Theorem 1 for admissible semantics.*

To argue the quality of P-SAF, it can be shown that it satisfies the rationality postulates introduced in (D’Agostino & Modgil, 2018; Amgoud & Besnard, 2013).

Definition 9. Let $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ be the corresponding P-SAF of a KB \mathcal{K} . Wrt. $\text{sem} \in \{\text{adm}, \text{stb}, \text{prf}, \text{grd}\}$, $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ is

1. closed under $\overline{\text{CN}}$ iff for all $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K})$, $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}) = \overline{\text{CN}}(\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E}))$;
2. consistent iff for all $\mathcal{E} \in \text{Exts}_{\text{sem}}(\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K})$, $\text{Cons}(\mathcal{E})$ is consistent;

Proposition 2. Wrt. to any semantics in $\{\text{adm}, \text{stb}, \text{prf}, \text{grd}\}$, $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ satisfies consistency, closure.

The proof of Proposition 2 is analogous to those of Proposition 2 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024). Because of this similarity, they are not included in the appendix.

Example 8 (Continue Example 6). Recall \mathcal{K}_1 . Table 2 shows the supports and conclusions of all arguments induced from \mathcal{K} . The corresponding P-SAF admits **stb** (**prf**) extensions: $\text{Exts}_{\text{stb/prf}}(\mathcal{AF}_1) = \{\mathcal{E}_1, \dots, \mathcal{E}_3\}$, where $\mathcal{E}_1 = \text{Args}(\{\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD}), \text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR}), \text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD}), \text{GC}(\text{KR})\})$ ⁷ = $\{A_5, A_6, A_2, A_4, A_0, A_7, A_3, A_8, A_9, A_{10}, A_{11}, A_{12}\}$, and $\mathcal{E}_2, \dots, \mathcal{E}_3$ are obtained in an analogous way. It can be seen that the extensions correspond to the repairs of the KBs (by Theorem 1).

Reconsider $q_1 = \text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$. We have that q_1 is credulously accepted under **stb** (**prf**) extensions. In other words, \mathbf{v} is a possible answer for q_1 .

Table 2: Supports and conclusions of arguments

Argument	Sup(A_i)	Con(A_i)
A_0	$\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})\}$	$\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})$
A_9	$\{\text{GC}(\text{KR})\}$	$\text{GC}(\text{KR})$
A_7	$\{\text{GC}(\text{KR}), \text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})\}$	$\text{FP}(\mathbf{v})$
A_1	$\{\text{GC}(\text{KR}), \text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})\}$	$\text{Re}(\mathbf{v})$
A_4	$\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})\}$	$\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})$
A_5	$\{\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})\}$	$\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})$
A_6	$\{\text{UC}(\text{KD})\}$	$\text{UC}(\text{KD})$
A_2	$\{\text{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD}), \text{UC}(\text{KD})\}$	$\text{TA}(\mathbf{v})$
A_3	$\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})\}$	$\text{Le}(\mathbf{v})$
A_8	$\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})\}$	$\text{Le}(\mathbf{v})$
A_{10}	$\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})\}$	$\text{Em}(\mathbf{v})$
A_{11}	$\{\text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KD})\}$	$\text{Em}(\mathbf{v})$
A_{12}	$\{\text{GC}(\text{KR}), \text{te}(\mathbf{v}, \text{KR})\}$	$\text{Em}(\mathbf{v})$

In this section, we have translated from KBs into P-SAFs, and shows that the acceptance of a formula ϕ of \mathcal{L} corresponds to the acceptance of a set of arguments \mathcal{A} for ϕ . When we say "a set of arguments \mathcal{A} for ϕ ", it means simply that for each argument in \mathcal{A} , its consequence is ϕ . We next introduce a novel notion of *explanatory dialogue* ("dialogue" for short) viewed as a *dialectical proof procedure* in Section 4. Section 5 shows how to use a dialogue to determine and explain the acceptance of ϕ w.r.t. argumentation semantics.

7. Fix $\mathcal{F}' \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, $\text{Args}(\mathcal{F}')$ is the set of arguments generated by \mathcal{F}'

4. Explanatory Dialogue Models

We have already seen the link between reasoning in P-SAFs and reasoning in MSCs in Section 3.2. Leveraging this connection, we now discuss how to determine the acceptance of a formula w.r.t. argumentation semantics. To this end, as inspired by (Prakken, 2006, 2005), we develop a *novel explanatory dialogue model* for P-SAFs, which examines the dispute process involving the exchange of arguments (represented as formulas in KBs) between two agents. This dispute process can be viewed as an explanation for the acceptance of a formula w.r.t. argumentation semantics, and thus for reasoning in abstract logic.

4.1 Basic Notions

Concepts of a novel dialogue model for P-SAFs include **utterances**, **dialogues** and **concrete dialogue trees** ("dialogue tree" for short). In this model, a topic language \mathcal{L}_t is an abstract logic (\mathcal{L}, CN) ; dialogues are sequences of utterances between two agents: a proponent P and an opponent O that share a common language \mathcal{L}_c . Utterances are defined as follows:

Definition 10 (Utterances). *An utterance of agents a , $a \in \{P, O\}$ has the form $u = (a, \text{TG}, \text{C}, \text{ID})$, where:*

- $\text{ID} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the identifier of the utterance,
- TG is the target of the utterance and we impose that $\text{TG} < \text{ID}$,
- $\text{C} \in \mathcal{L}_c$ (the content) is one of the following forms: Fix $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ and $\Delta \subseteq \mathcal{L}$.
 - $\text{claim}(\phi)$: The agent asserts that ϕ is the case,
 - $\text{offer}(\Delta, \phi)$: The agent advances grounds Δ for ϕ uttered by the previously advanced utterances such that $\phi \in \text{CN}(\Delta)$,
 - $\text{contrary}(\Delta, \phi)$: The agent advances the formulas Δ that are contrary to ϕ uttered by the previously advanced utterance,
 - $\text{concede}(\phi)$: The agent gives up debating and admits that ϕ is the case,
 - $\text{fact}(\phi)$: The agent asserts that ϕ is a fact in \mathcal{K} .
 - κ : The agent does not have or wants to contribute information at that point in the dialogue.

We denote by \mathcal{U} the set of all utterances.

To determine which utterances agents can make to construct a dialogue, we define a notion of *legal move*, similarly to communication protocols. For any two utterances $u_i, u_j \in \mathcal{U}$, $u_i \neq u_j$, we say that:

- u_i is the *target utterance* of u_j iff the target of u_j is the identifier of u_i , i.e., $u_i = (-, -, \text{C}_i, \text{ID})$ and $u_j = (-, \text{ID}, \text{C}_j, -)$;
- u_j is the *legal move* after u_i iff u_i is the target utterance of u_j and one of the following cases in Table 3 holds.

Table 3: Locutions and responses

Locution u_i	Available responses u_j
$C_i = \text{claim}(\phi)$	(1) $C_j = \text{offer}(-, \phi)$ if $\phi \in \text{CN}(\{-\})$, (2) $C_j = \text{fact}(\phi)$ if $\phi \in \mathcal{K}$, (3) $C_j = \text{contrary}(-, \phi)$ where $\{-, \phi\}$ is inconsistent;
$C_i = \text{fact}(\phi)$	$C_j = \text{contrary}(-, \phi)$ where $\{-, \phi\}$ is inconsistent;
$C_i = \text{offer}(\Delta, \phi)$ with $\phi \in \text{CN}(\Delta)$	(1) $C_j = \text{contrary}(-, \phi)$ where $\{-, \phi\}$ is inconsistent, (2) $C_j = \text{contrary}(-, \beta)$ where $\beta \in \Delta$ and $\{-\} \cup \{\beta\}$ is inconsistent, (3) $C_j = \text{offer}(-, \beta_i)$ with $\beta_i \in \Delta$ and $\beta_j \in \text{CN}(\{-\})$
$C_i = \text{contrary}(\beta, -)$	(1) $C_j = \text{contrary}(-, \beta)$ where $\{-, \beta\}$ is inconsistent (2) $C_j = \text{offer}(-, \beta)$ with $\beta \in \text{CN}(\{-\})$.
$C_i = \text{concede}(\phi)$	There is no response, and the dialogue ends.

An utterance is a legal move after another if any of the following cases happen: (1) the utterance with the content **offer** contributes to expanding an argument; (2) the utterance with the content **fact** identifies a fact in support of an argument; (3) the utterance with content **contrary** starts the construction of a counter-argument. An utterance can be from the same agent or not.

4.2 Dialogues and Dialogue Trees

In essence, a dialogue is a sequence of utterances u_1, \dots, u_n , each of which transforms the dialogue from one state to another. To keep track of information disclosed in dialogues for P-SAFs, we define *dialogue trees* constructed as the dialogue progresses.

A dialogue tree represents a dispute progress between the proponent P and the opponent O who take turns exchanging arguments in the form of formulas of a KB. The idea is that P aims at showing that such a formula can be justified, while O challenges P with the implications of P's own position. If P is able to counter-attack all of O's moves, P yields a justification for the target. Informally, in a dialogue tree, the formula of each node represents an argument's conclusion or elements of the argument's support. A node is annotated *unmarked* if its formula is only mentioned in the claim, but without any further examination, *marked-non-fact* if its formula is the logical consequence of previous uttered formulas, and *marked-fact* if its formula has been explicitly uttered as a fact in \mathcal{K} . A node is labelled P (O) if it is (directly or indirectly) for (against, respectively) the claim of the dialogue. The ID is used to identify the node's corresponding utterance in the dialogue. The nodes are connected in two cases: (1) they belong to the same argument, and (2) they form collective attacks between arguments. We formally define dialogue trees and dialogues.

Definition 11. *Given a sequence of utterances $\delta = u_1, \dots, u_n$, the **dialogue tree** $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ drawn from δ for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ is a tree whose nodes are tuples $(S, [T, L, ID])$, where:*

- S is a formula in \mathcal{L} ,
- T is either **um** (unmarked), **nf** (marked-non-fact), **fa** (marked-fact),
- L is either P or O,
- ID is the identifier of the utterance u_i ;

and $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is \mathcal{T}^n in the sequence $\mathcal{T}^1, \dots, \mathcal{T}^n$ constructed inductively from δ , as follows:

1. \mathcal{T}^1 contains a single node: $(\phi, [\mathbf{um}, \mathbf{P}, \mathbf{id}_1])$ where \mathbf{id}_1 is the identifier of the utterance $u_1 = (-, -, \mathbf{claim}(\phi), \mathbf{id}_1)$;
2. Let $u_{i+1} = (-, -, \mathbf{ta}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{id})$ be the utterance in δ ; \mathcal{T}^i be the i -th tree with the utterance $(-, -, \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{ta}}, \mathbf{ta})$ as the target utterance of u_{i+1} . Then \mathcal{T}^{i+1} is obtained from \mathcal{T}^i by u_{i+1} , if one of the following conditions holds: $(\mathbf{L}, \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{ta}} \in \{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{O}\}, \mathbf{L} \neq \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{ta}})$:
 - a) If $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{offer}(\Delta, \alpha)$ with $\Delta = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\}$ and $\alpha \in \mathbf{CN}(\Delta)$, then \mathcal{T}^{i+1} is obtained:
 - For all $\beta_j \in \Delta$, new nodes $(\beta_j, [\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{id}])$ are added as children of the node $(\alpha, [-, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{ta}])$ of \mathcal{T}^i . Here $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{fa}$ if $\beta_j \in \mathcal{K}$, otherwise $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{nf}$;
 - The node $(\alpha, [-, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{ta}])$ is replaced by $(\alpha, [\mathbf{nf}, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{ta}])$;
 - b) If $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{fact}(\alpha)$ then \mathcal{T}^{i+1} is \mathcal{T}^i with the node $(\alpha, [-, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{ta}])$ replaced by $(\alpha, [\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{id}])$;
 - c) If $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{contrary}(\Delta, \alpha)$ where $\Delta = \{\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m\}$ and $\Delta \cup \{\alpha\}$ is inconsistent, then \mathcal{T}^{i+1} is obtained by adding new nodes $(\beta_j, [\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{L}, \mathbf{id}])$, ($\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{fa}$ if $\beta_j \in \mathcal{K}$, otherwise $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{nf}$), as children of the node $(\alpha, [\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{ta}}, \mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{ta}}, \mathbf{ta}])$ of \mathcal{T}^i , where $\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{ta}} \in \{\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{nf}\}$.

For such dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$, the nodes labelled by \mathbf{P} (resp., \mathbf{O}) are called the proponent nodes (resp., opponent nodes). We call the sequence u_1, \dots, u_n a **dialogue** $D(\phi)$ for ϕ where ϕ is the formula of the root in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.

This dialogue tree can be seen as a concrete representation of an *abstract dialogue tree* defined in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024). Here, the nodes represent formulas and the edges display either the monotonic inference steps used to construct arguments or the attack relations between arguments. A group of nodes in a dialogue tree with the same label \mathbf{P} (or \mathbf{O}) corresponds to the proponent (or opponent) argument in the abstract dialogue tree.

If there are no utterances for both proponents and opponents in a dialogue tree from a dialogue δ , then δ is called *terminated*. Note that a dialogue can be "incomplete", which means that it ends before the utterances related to determining success are claimed. To prevent this from happening we assume that dialogues are *complete*, i.e. that there are no "unsaid" utterances (with the content **fact**, **offer** or **contrary**) in such dialogue that would bring important arguments to determine success. This assumption will ease the proof of the soundness and completeness result later.

Example 9 (Continue Example 8). *When users received the answer "(v) is possible researcher", they would like to know "Why is this the case?". The system will explain to the users through the natural language dispute agreement that the agent P is persuading O to agree that v is a researcher. This dispute agreement is formally modelled by an explanatory dialogue $D(\mathbf{Re}(v)) = \delta$ as in Figure 1.*

P	O
$u_1 = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{O}, \mathbf{claim}(\mathbf{Re}(v)), 1)$	
$u_2 = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{offer}(\mathbf{FP}(v), \mathbf{Re}(v)), 2)$	
$u_3 = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{2}, \mathbf{offer}(\{\mathbf{te}(v, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR})\}, \mathbf{FP}(v)), 3)$	
	$u_4 = (\mathbf{O}, \mathbf{2}, \mathbf{contrary}(\mathbf{TA}(v), \mathbf{Re}(v)), 4)$
	$u_5 = (\mathbf{O}, \mathbf{4}, \mathbf{offer}(\{\mathbf{taOf}(v, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{UC}(\mathbf{KD})\}, \mathbf{TA}(v)), 5)$
$u_6 = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{4}, \mathbf{contrary}(\mathbf{Le}(v), \mathbf{TA}(v)), 6)$	
$u_7 = (\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{6}, \mathbf{offer}(\mathbf{te}(v, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{Le}(v)), 7)$	
	$u_8 = (\mathbf{O}, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{concede}(\mathbf{Re}(v)), 8)$

Figure 1: Given \mathcal{L}_t is \mathcal{K}_1 , a dialogue $D(\mathbf{Re}(v)) = u_1, \dots, u_9$ for $q_1 = \mathbf{Re}(v)$

Figure 2 illustrates how to fully construct a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ from $D(\text{Re}(v)) = \delta$. To avoid confusing users, after the construction processing, we obtain the final dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ with necessary labels, such as formulas, P and O, in Figure 3. The line indicates that children conflict with their parents. The dotted line indicates that children are implied from their parents by inference rules. From this tree, the system provides a dialogical explanation in natural language as shown in Example 1.

Figure 2: Construction of the dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta) = \mathcal{T}_7(\delta)$ drawn from $D(\text{Re}(v))$.

Figure 3: A final version of the dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ after construction

We have already introduced the definitions of dialogues and dialogue trees. To determine and explain the acceptance of a formula ϕ w.r.t. argumentation semantics, one needs to consider whether a dialogue for ϕ is *successful* according to a certain *winning condition*. Intuitively, a successful dialogue for ϕ can be viewed as a *dialectical proof procedure* that generates the dialogue tree capturing the properties of the considered semantics. The construction of such a tree indicates the existence of a set of potential arguments, including the potential argument for ϕ , that sanctions the considered semantics. In other words, dialogue trees with the properties of argumentation semantics are subsequently used to determine *successful dialogues* w.r.t argumentation semantics. In the following sections, we will examine the "winning conditions" for a *successful dialogue* that constructs the dialogue tree satisfying the properties of argumentation semantics. For the purposes of this paper, we use the terms "dialectical proof procedure" and "dialogue" interchangeably.

Before continuing, let us introduce notions that will be useful in the next sections. These include **potential argument** obtained from a dialogue tree, **(collective) potential attacks** against a potential argument in a tree, and **P-SAF** drawn from a dialogue tree.

A *potential argument* is an argument obtained from a dialogue tree.

Definition 12. A potential argument obtained from a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is a sub-tree \mathcal{T}^s of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ such that:

- all nodes in \mathcal{T}^s are labeled identically with either P or O;
- if there is an utterance $(-, -, \text{offer}(\Delta, \alpha), \text{id})$ and a node $(\beta_i, [-, \text{L}, \text{id}])$ in \mathcal{T}^s with $\beta_i \in \Delta$, then all the nodes $(\beta_1, [-, \text{L}, \text{id}]), \dots, (\beta_m, [-, \text{L}, \text{id}])$ are in \mathcal{T}^s
- for every node $(\alpha, [\text{nf}, \text{L}, -])$ in \mathcal{T}^s , all its immediate children in \mathcal{T}^s have the same identifier (they belong to a single utterance).

The formula ϕ in the root of \mathcal{T}^s is the conclusion. The set of the formulas H held by the descended nodes in \mathcal{T}^s , i.e., $H = \{\beta \mid (\beta, [\text{fa}, -, -]) \text{ is a node in } \mathcal{T}^s\}$, is the support of \mathcal{T}^s . A potential argument obtained from a dialogue tree is a proponent (opponent) argument if its nodes are labelled P (O, respectively).

To shorten notation, we use the term "an argument for ϕ " instead of the term "an argument with the conclusion ϕ ".

Example 10 (Continue Example 9). Figure 4 (Right) shows the potential arguments obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.

Potential arguments correspond to the conventional P-SAF arguments.

Lemma 1. A potential argument \mathcal{T}^s corresponds to an argument for ϕ supported by H as in conventional P-SAF (in Definition 5).

Proof. This lemma is trivially true as a node in a potential argument can be mapped to a node in a conventional P-SAF argument (in Definition 5) by dropping the tag T and the identifier ID. □

We introduce (*collective*) *potential attacks* against a potential argument, or a sub-tree, in a dialogue tree. This states that a potential argument is *attacked* when there exist nodes within the tree that are children of the argument. Formally:

Definition 13. Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a dialogue tree and \mathcal{T}^s be a potential argument obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. \mathcal{T}^s is attacked iff there is a node $N = (\mathbf{L}, [\mathbf{T}, -, -])$ in \mathcal{T}^s , with $\mathbf{L} \in \{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{O}\}$ and $\mathbf{T} \in \{\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{nf}\}$, such that N has children M_1, \dots, M_k labelled by $\mathbf{L}' \in \{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{O}\} \setminus \{\mathbf{L}\}$ in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ and the children have the same identifier.

We say that the sub-trees rooted at M_j ($1 \leq j \leq k$) attacks \mathcal{T}^s .

For brevity, we use "collective attacks" instead of "(collective) potential attacks".

Definition 14. (A) P-SAF drawn from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is $\mathcal{AF}_\delta = (\mathbf{Arg}_\delta, \mathbf{Att}_\delta)$, where \mathbf{Arg}_δ is the set of potential arguments obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$, \mathbf{Att}_δ contains the attacks between the potential arguments.

Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is drawn from δ , we can say \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ or the *potential* P-SAF \mathcal{AF}_δ instead. We use the terms interchangeably.

As in (Dung et al., 2006), two useful concepts that are used for our soundness result in the next sections are the *defence set* and the *culprits* of a dialogue tree.

Definition 15. Given a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$,

- The defence set $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$ is the set of all facts α in proponent nodes of the form $N = (\alpha, [\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{P}, -])$ such that N is in a potential argument;
- The culprits $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$ is the set of facts β in opponent nodes $N = (\beta, [\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{O}, -])$ such that N has the child node $N' = (-, [-, \mathbf{P}, -])$ and N and N' are in potential arguments.

Example 11. Figure 4 (Left) gives the focused dialogue tree drawn from the dialogue $D(\mathbf{Re}(\mathbf{v}))$ in Example 9. The defence set is $\{\mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{GC}(\mathbf{KR}), \mathbf{te}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KD})\}$; the culprits is $\{\mathbf{taOf}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{KD}), \mathbf{UC}(\mathbf{KD})\}$.

Figure 4: Left: A focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ drawn from $D(\mathbf{Re}(\mathbf{v}))$ in Table 1. Right: Some potential argument obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.

5. Computing the Acceptability of a Formula in P-SAFs

We discuss how dialogues and dialogue trees are used to determine the acceptance of a formula w.r.t. argumentation semantics, and demonstrate the connection between dialogue-based argumentative reasoning and inconsistency-tolerant reasoning. Complementing our theoretical results, we outline a general algorithm for computing the acceptance of a formula under consideration. The idea is to (1) construct dialogue trees for a given formula, and (2) check whether any of these trees satisfy the properties required by the considered semantics. To implement the general algorithm, we present three algorithms: *Defensive-Finite*, *Defensive-Nonredundant* and *Ideal* algorithms, which are discussed in the following sections.

Algorithm 1: A general algorithm for computing the acceptance of ϕ

Input: A knowledge base \mathcal{K} and a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$

Output: the acceptance of ϕ w.r.t. **sem** semantics, with $\mathbf{sem} \in \{\mathbf{prf}, \mathbf{adm}, \mathbf{grd}\}$;

Local variables:

$Tree_{DF}$ be a set of defensive and finite trees;

$Tree_{ID}$ be a set of ideal trees;

$Tree_{DN}$ be a set of defensive and non-redundant trees;

1 Construct a set of potential arguments for ϕ $Roots := \text{Construction}(\mathcal{K}, \phi)$;

2 **for** $A \in Roots$ **do**

3 $T := \text{Ideal}(A)$

4 **if** $T \neq \emptyset$ **then**

5 add T to $Tree_{ID}$;

6 Continue;

7 **else**

8 $T := \text{Defensive-Nonredundant}(\{\{A\}, \emptyset, \{A\}, \emptyset\})$;

9 **if** $T \neq \emptyset$ **then**

10 add T to $Tree_{DN}$;

11 Continue;

12 **else**

13 $T := \text{Defensive-Finite}(\{\{A\}, \emptyset, \{A\}, \emptyset\})$

14 **if** $T \neq \emptyset$ **then**

15 add T to $Trees_{DF}$

16 **if** $Tree_{ID} \neq \emptyset$ **then** ϕ is sceptically accepted;

17 **else if** $Tree_{DN} \neq \emptyset$ **then** ϕ is credulously accepted under **prf** semantics;

18 **else if** $Tree_{DF} \neq \emptyset$ **then** ϕ is groundedly accepted under **adm** semantics;

19 **else** ϕ is not accepted;

5.1 Computing Credulous Acceptance

This section presents the computation of credulous acceptance for a formula under admissible/ preferred semantics. We analyze the dialogue tree properties, propose an algorithm for computing credulous acceptance, and establish the soundness and completeness. To

determine the credulous acceptance for a formula under consideration $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ w.r.t. argumentation semantics, we verify the non-deterministic algorithm:

1. Guess a set of potential arguments.
2. Verify that the set is an extension and that it satisfies the properties of the considered semantics.
3. Verify that ϕ is in the conclusions of the set or not in it, respectively.

These steps can be implemented through a dialogue that generates the dialogue tree capturing the properties of the considered semantics. For admissible semantics, we need to show that there exists at least an admissible set of potential arguments that is conflict-free, defends itself, and includes the argument for ϕ . This means that we need to ensure "winning conditions" for an *admissible-successful dialogue* that constructs the dialogue tree satisfying the properties of admissible semantics. In what follows, let us sketch the idea of a dialectical proof procedure for computing the credulous acceptance as follows: Assume that a (dispute) dialogue between the agents P and O in which P persuades O about its belief " ϕ is accepted". Two agents take alternating turns in exchanging their arguments in the form of formulas. When the (dispute) dialogue progresses, we are increasingly building, starting from the root ϕ , a dialogue tree. Each node of such tree, labelled with either P or O, corresponds to an utterance played by the agent. The credulous acceptance of ϕ is proven if P can win the game by ending the dialogue in its favour according to a "*last-word*" principle. To ensure that the set of potential arguments advanced by P in the dialogue tree is admissible (i.e., conflict-free and defends arguments in it), the rules governing legal moves in the dialogue are designed to ensure that the dialogue tree possesses the properties of *defensiveness* and *non-redundancy*. To facilitate our idea, we introduce the properties of a dialogue tree: *focus*, *patience*, *last-word*, *defensiveness*, and *non-redundancy*.

5.1.1 PROPERTIES OF DIALOGUE TREES

We first introduce a notion of *focused dialogue trees*. This concept is useful because it allows us to show a *correspondence principle* between dialogue trees and *abstract dialogue trees* defined in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)⁸. By the correspondence principle, we can utilize the results from (Ho & Schlobach, 2024) to obtain the important results in the next sections.

Observe that a dialogue δ can be seen as a collection of several (independent) *focused sub-dialogues* $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_n$. The dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from the focused sub-dialogue δ_i is a subtree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ and corresponds to the abstract dialogue tree (defined in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)) (for an argument for ϕ). Each such subtree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ has the properties: (1) ϕ is supported by a single proponent argument; (2) An opponent argument is attacked by either a single proponent argument or a set of collective proponent arguments; (3) A proponent argument can be attacked by either multiple single opponent arguments or sets of collective opponent arguments. We call a tree with these properties the *focused dialogue tree*.

8. We reproduce the notion of abstract dialogue trees and introduce the correspondence principle in Appendix A. Here we briefly describe the concept of abstract dialogue trees: an abstract dialogue tree is a tree where nodes are labeled with arguments, and edges represent attacks between arguments.

Definition 16 (Focused sub-dialogues). δ' is called a focused sub-dialogue of a dialogue δ iff it is a dialogue for ϕ and, for all utterances $u \in \delta'$, $u \in \delta$. We say that δ is the full-dialogue of δ' and $\mathcal{T}(\delta')$ drawn from δ' is the sub-tree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.

Definition 17 (Focused dialogue trees). A dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is focused iff

1. all the immediate children of the root node have the same identifier (that is, are part of a single utterance);
2. all the children labelled P of each potential argument labelled O have the same identifier (that is, are part of a single utterance)

In Definition 17, we call child of a potential argument a node that is child of any of the nodes of the potential argument.

Remark 6. Focused dialogue trees and their relation to abstract dialogue trees are crucial to prove the results in Section 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. We refer to Appendix B for details.

Figure 5: Left: A non-focused dialogue tree. Right: A focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1)$.

Example 12. Consider a query $q_3 = A(a)$ to a KB $\mathcal{K}_3 = (\mathcal{R}_3, \mathcal{C}_3, \mathcal{F}_3)$ where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_3 &= \{r_1 : C(x) \wedge B(x) \rightarrow A(x), r_2 : D(x) \rightarrow A(x)\} \\ \mathcal{C}_3 &= \{D(x) \wedge C(x) \rightarrow \perp, E(x) \wedge C(x) \rightarrow \perp\} \\ \mathcal{F}_3 &= \{B(a), C(a), D(a), E(a)\} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5 (Left) shows a non-focused dialogue tree drawn for a dialogue $D(A(a)) = \delta$. Figure 5 (Right) shows a focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1)$ drawn for a sub-dialogue δ_1 of δ . This tree is the sub-tree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.

We restrict dialogue trees to be *patient*. This means that agents wait until a potential argument has been fully constructed before beginning to attack it. Formally: A dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is *patient* iff for all nodes $N = (-, [\mathbf{fa}, -, -])$ in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$, N is in (the support of) a potential argument obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. Through this paper, the term "dialogue trees" refers to *patient dialogue trees*.

We present the "last-word" principle to specify a winning condition for the proponent, i.e., P wins if either P finishes the dialogue tree with the un-attacked facts (Item 1), or any attacks used by O have been attacked with valid counter attacks (Item 2). Formally:

Definition 18. A focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is last-word iff

1. for all leaf nodes N in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$, N is the form of $(-, [\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{P}, -])$, and
2. if a node N is of the form $(-, [\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{O}, -])$ with $\mathbf{T} \in \{\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{nf}\}$, then N is in a potential argument and N is properly attacked.

In the above definition, we say that a node N of a potential argument is attacked, meaning that N has children labelled by \mathbf{P} with the same identifier.

The definition of "last-word" incorporates the requirement that a set of potential arguments \mathcal{S} (supported by the defence set) attacks every attack against \mathcal{S} . However, it does not include the requirement that \mathcal{S} does not attack itself. This requirement is incorporated in the definition of *defensive dialogue trees*.

Definition 19. A focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is defensive iff it is

- last-word, and
- no formulas Δ in opponent nodes belong to $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$ such that $\Delta \cup \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$ is inconsistent.

In admissible dialogue trees, nodes labelled \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{O} within potential arguments can have common facts when considering potential arguments that attack or defend others. However, potential arguments with nodes sharing common facts cannot attack proponent potential arguments whose facts are in the defence set. Let us show this in the following example.

Figure 6: Left: A focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$. Middle: An infinite dialogue tree. Right: Arguments of \mathcal{AF}_4 .

Example 13. Consider a query $q_4 = A(a)$ to a KB $\mathcal{K}_4 = (\mathcal{R}_4, \mathcal{C}_4, \mathcal{F}_4)$ where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_4 &= \emptyset \\ \mathcal{C}_4 &= \{c_1 : A(x) \wedge B(x) \wedge C(x) \rightarrow \perp\} \\ \mathcal{F}_4 &= \{A(a), B(a), C(a)\} \end{aligned}$$

Consider the focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ (see Figure 6 (Left)) drawn from the focused sub-dialogue δ_i of a dialogue $D(A(a)) = \delta$. The defence set $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \{A(a), C(a)\}$; the

culprits $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \{B(a), C(a)\}$. We have $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) \cap \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \{C(a)\}$. It can be seen that $\{C(a)\} \cup \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ is consistent. In other words, there exists a potential argument, say A , such that $\{C(a)\}$ is the support of A , and A cannot attack any proponent argument supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$. Clearly, $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ have the common formula, but the set of arguments supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ does not attack itself.

From the above observation, it follows immediately that.

Lemma 2. *Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a defensive dialogue tree. The set of proponent arguments (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$) does not attack itself in the P-SAF drawn from δ .*

Consider the following dialogue to see why the "non-redundant" property is necessary.

Example 14. *Consider*

To ensure credulous acceptance, all possible opponent arguments must be accounted for. But if such a parent of proponent argument is already in the dialogue tree, then deploying it will not help the opponent win the dialogue. To avoid this, a dialogue tree must be *non-redundant*. This property prevents the opponent argument from repeating more than once, i.e., it forbids to bring forward the same counter-arguments multiple times, thereby eliminating infinite branches in the tree.

Definition 20. *A focused dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is non-redundant iff every node N_1 of a potential argument of the form $(\alpha, [\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{P}, \mathbf{id}_1])$, where $\mathbf{T} \in \{\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{nf}\}$, has children N_j of the form $(\beta_j, [\mathbf{fa}, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{id}_j])$ such that no N_j are parents of N_1 of the potential argument.*

In Definition 20, we call the parent of a potential argument a node that is parent of any of the nodes of the potential argument.

5.1.2 ALGORITHMS

We have introduced the desired properties of dialogue trees to compute credulous acceptance. We now sketch out how an algorithm for the credulous acceptance problems can be implemented. To implement Step(1) and (2) of the algorithm, we present a **Defensive-Nonredundant** procedure and sub-procedures: A **Construction** procedure to find potential arguments for a formula, by Definition 5; and an **Attack** procedure to return a set of potential arguments collectively attacking a potential argument, by Definition 6 (These two procedures are discussed in Section ?? in detail). The idea is that, given a potential argument A for $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$, the Defensive-Nonredundant procedure presents a top-down construction of defensive and non-redundant dialogue trees with root A (as defined in Definition 19 and 20, respectively) by sequences of tuples of the form (P_i, O_i, DE_i, AT_i) where P_i (resp., O_i) is the set of potential arguments whose nodes are labelled by P (resp. 0). These potential arguments are generated by the Construction procedure. DE_i denotes the set of potential arguments presented by the proponent up to step i (So $P_i \subseteq DE_i$); AT_i denotes the set of potential arguments presented by the opponent and counterattacked by the proponent so far (so the opponent has presented $O_i \cup AT_i$). At each step, the dialogue tree is expanded by selecting a frontier node labelled by a potential argument B and its replacement by some of its children (because it is unnecessary to reconsider children already attacked).

The defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree will present the set of proponent's potential arguments DE that includes the potential argument for ϕ . To ensure that DE is admissible, the algorithm sets checking conditions: Let $\mathbf{Base}(DE) = \bigcup_{E \in DE} \mathbf{Sup}(E)$ be the supports of the potential arguments in DE , and \mathbf{Attack}_B be the set of potential arguments collectively attacking the argument B (which is computed by the Attack procedure). (a) One checks the defensiveness (Line 5), i.e., if $B \in P_i$ then no formulas $\Delta \subseteq \mathbf{Base}(\mathbf{Attack}_B \cap DE_i)$ such that $\Delta \cup \mathbf{Base}(DE_i)$ is inconsistent (an argument B of the proponent is not attacked by his other argument in DE_i); (b) One checks the non-redundancy (Line 7-8), if $B \in O_i$ then the proponent does not use argument in $AT_i \cup O_i$ to avoid later conflicts in $DE_j, j > i$.

Algorithm 2: Defensive-Nonredundant(T_0)

Input: A KB \mathcal{K} and $T_0 = \{(\{A\}, \emptyset, \{A\}, \emptyset)\}$ where A is a potential argument for ϕ
Output: A defensive and non-redundant tree T

- 1 Initiate $T := T_0$
- 2 **while** *not* (a tuple of T has the form $(\emptyset, \emptyset, DE, AT)$) **do**
- 3 Select $t = (P, O, DE, AT) \in T$ and $B \in P$ or $B \in O$
- 4 Remove t from T
- 5 **if** $B \in P$, and no formulas $\Delta \subseteq \mathbf{Base}(\mathbf{Attack}_B \cap DE)$ s.t. $\Delta \cup \mathbf{Base}(DE_i)$ is inconsistent, where $\mathbf{Attack}_B = \{\mathbf{Attack}(B)\}$ **then**
- 6 Add $(P \setminus \{B\}, O \cup (\mathbf{Attack}_B \setminus AT), DE, AT)$ to T
- 7 **if** $B \in O$ **then**
- 8 **for** each $C \in \mathbf{Attack}_B \setminus (AT \cup O)$ **do**
- 9 Add $(P \cup \{C\}, O \setminus \mathbf{Attacked}_C, DE \cup \{C\}, AT \cup (\mathbf{Attacked}_C \cap O))$ to T , where $\mathbf{Attacked}_C = \{\mathbf{Attack}(C)\}$
- 10 **return** T

In the following, we establish the soundness w.r.t. admissible semantics.

Theorem 2. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ such that it is defensive and non-redundant, then*

- δ is admissible-successful;
- ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$).

The proof of this theorem is in Appendix B.

We can define a notion of *preferred-successful dialogue* with a formula accepted under preferred semantics in the P-SAF framework drawn from the dialogue. Since every admissible set (of arguments) is necessarily contained in a preferred set (see (Dung, 1995; Nielsen & Parsons, 2007)), and every preferred set is admissible by definition, trivially a dialogue is preferred-successful iff it is admissible-successful. The following theorem is analogous to Theorem 2 for preferred semantics.

Theorem 3. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ such that it is defensive and non-redundant, then δ is preferred-successful and ϕ is credulously accepted under **prf** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$).*

Sketch. The proof of this theory follows the fact that every preferred dialogue tree is an admissible dialogue tree. Thus, the proof of this theorem is analogous to those of Theorem 2. \square

Remark 7. We can similarly define a notion of stable dialogue trees for a formula accepted under **stb** in the P-SAF. Since stable and preferred sets coincide, trivially a dialogue tree is stable iff it is defensive and non-redundant. Thus we can use the result of Theorem 3 for stable semantics.

We now discuss the completeness results. In this work, dialogues viewed as dialectical proof procedures are sound but not always complete in general. The reason is that the dialectical proof procedures might enter a non-terminating loop during the process of argument constructions, which leads to the incompleteness w.r.t. admissible semantics. To illustrate this, we refer to Example 1 using logic programming in (Thang, Dung, & Pooksook, 2022) for an explanation. We also provide another example using Datalog $^\pm$.

Example 15. Consider a query $q_6 = P(a)$ to a Datalog $^\pm$ KB $\mathcal{K}_6 = (\mathcal{R}_6, \mathcal{C}_6, \mathcal{F}_6)$ where

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{R}_6 &= \{r_1 : P(x) \rightarrow Q(x), r_2 : Q(x) \rightarrow P(x)\} \\ \mathcal{C}_6 &= \{P(x) \wedge R(x) \rightarrow \perp\} \\ \mathcal{F}_6 &= \{P(a), R(a)\}\end{aligned}$$

The semantics of the corresponding P-SAF \mathcal{AF}_4 are determined by the arguments illustrated in Figure 6 (Right). The result should state that " $P(a)$ is a possible answer" as the argument B_1 for $P(a)$ is credulously accepted under the admissible sets $\{B_1\}$ and $\{B_2\}$ of \mathcal{AF}_4 . But the dialectical proof procedures fail to deliver the admissible set $\{B_1\}$ w.r.t. \mathcal{AF}_4 as they could not overcome the non-termination of the process to construct an argument B_1 for $P(a)$ due to the "infinite loop".

Intuitively, since the dialogues as dialectical proof procedures (implicitly) incorporate the computation of arguments top-down, the process of argument construction should be finite (also known as finite tree-derivations in the sense of Definition 5) to achieve the completeness results. Thus, we restrict the attention to decidable logic with cycle-restricted conditions that its corresponding P-SAF framework produces arguments to be computed finitely in a top-down fashion. For example, given a Datalog $^\pm$ KB $\mathcal{K} = (\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{F})$, the *dependency graph* of the KB as defined in (Hecham, Bisquert, & Croitoru, 2017) consists of the vertices representing the atoms and the edges from an atom u to v iff v is obtained from u (possibly with other atoms) by the application of a rule in \mathcal{R} . The intuition behind the use of the dependency graph is that no infinite tree-derivation exists if the dependency graph of KB is acyclic. By restricting such acyclic dependency graph condition, the process of argument construction in the corresponding P-SAF of the KB \mathcal{K} will be finite, which leads to the completeness of the dialogues w.r.t argumentation semantics. In the following, we show the completeness result w.r.t. admissible semantics.

Theorem 4. Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$) and δ is admissible-successful, then there is a defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .

The proof of this theorem is in Appendix C.

The following theorem is analogous to Theorem 4 for preferred semantics.

Theorem 5. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is credulously accepted under **prf** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$) and δ is preferred-successful, then there is a defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .*

Sketch. The proof of this theory follows the fact that every preferred-successful dialogue is an admissible-successful dialogue. Thus, the proof of this theorem is analogous to those of Theorem 4. \square

5.2 Computing Sceptical Acceptance

This section discusses the computation of sceptical acceptance for a formula under admissible and preferred semantics. We examine the properties of dialogue trees, introduce an algorithm for computing sceptical acceptance and establish the soundness and completeness results.

To determine the sceptical acceptance of an argument for ϕ , we verify the following:

1. There exists an admissible set of potential arguments S that includes the potential argument for ϕ ;
2. For each potential argument A attacking the potential arguments for ϕ in S , there exists no admissible set of potential arguments containing A .

For (1), we compute the credulously accepted arguments for ϕ (w.r.t. preferred semantics), and for (2), we consider the set of potential arguments that are credulously accepted but not attacked by any credulous accepted argument. These steps can be interpreted through the following "winning conditions" for a *sceptical successful dialogue* as follows:

- i. P wins the game by ending the dialogue,
- ii. none of O wins by the same line of reasoning.

This perspective allows us to introduce a notion of *ideal dialogue trees*.

Definition 21. *A defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is ideal iff none of the opponent arguments obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ belongs to an admissible set of potential arguments in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.*

In what follows, we will present an algorithm for computing sceptical acceptance.

5.2.1 ALGORITHMS

We show how the algorithm for computing sceptical acceptance is implemented. As discussed, the algorithm needs to construct an ideal dialogue tree for ϕ (defined in Definition 21). The ideal dialogue tree must satisfy two conditions:

- (i) It has an admissible set including a potential argument for ϕ , which fulfills Step (1).

(ii) None of the opponent's potential arguments belongs to the admissible set, which fulfills Step (2) of the algorithm.

From these, the algorithm is mainly based on *two key procedures*:

- For (i), one uses the **Defensive-Nonredundant** procedure for computing the credulously accepted arguments, which is introduced in Section 5.1.

- For (ii), one uses a **FullTree** procedure for characterizing all preferred extensions containing a given argument. Algorithm 3 in the **FullTree** procedure computes all preferred extensions that includes a given argument. It slightly modifies Algorithm 2 in the condition of the while loop. More concretely, Algorithm 3 constructs T_0, T_1, \dots, T_n such that T_n contains only tuples of the $(\emptyset, \emptyset, DE, AT)$. In contrast, Algorithm 2 constructs T_0, T_1, \dots, T_n such that T_n consists of at least one tuple of the form $(\emptyset, \emptyset, DE, AT)$.

Algorithm 3: FullTree(T_0)

Input: A KB \mathcal{K} and $T_0 := \{(\{A\}, \emptyset, \{A\}, \emptyset)\}$ where A is a potential argument for ϕ

Output: A full tree T

```

1 Initiate  $T := T_0$ 
2 while not (all tuples of  $T$  have the form  $(\emptyset, \emptyset, DE, AT)$ ) do
3   Select  $t = (P, O, DE, AT) \in T$  and  $B \in P$  or  $B \in O$ 
4   Remove  $t$  from  $T$ 
5   if  $B \in P$ , and no formulas  $\Delta \subseteq \text{Base}(\text{Attack}_B \cap DE)$  s.t.  $\Delta \cup \text{Base}(DE_i)$  is
      inconsistent, where  $\text{Attack}_B = \{\text{Attack}(B)\}$  then
6     Add  $(P \setminus \{B\}, O \cup (\text{Attack}_B \setminus AT), DE, AT)$  to  $T$ 
7   if  $B \in O$  then
8     for each  $C \in \text{Attack}_B \setminus (AT \cup O)$  do
9       Add  $(P \cup \{C\}, O \setminus \text{Attacked}_C, DE \cup \{C\}, AT \cup (\text{Attacked}_C \cap O))$  to  $T$ ,
          where  $\text{Attacked}_C = \{\text{Attack}(C)\}$ 
10 return  $T$ 

```

To compute ideal dialogue trees, Algorithm 4 starts the Defensive-Nonredundant procedure to find an admissible set DE defending a potential argument A for ϕ (at Line 3), then constructs a full dialogue tree against $\{B \mid B \in DE\}$ (at Line 7 - 12). If it fails in the second step, it needs to resume the first step to find another admissible set defending A . If it succeeds, then Algorithm 4 returns an ideal tree with root A .

Algorithm 4: Ideal(A)

Input: A KB \mathcal{K} and a potential argument A for ϕ
Output: An ideal tree with root A w.r.t **sem** semantics with $\mathbf{sem} \in \{\mathbf{adm}, \mathbf{prf}\}$

```

1  $T_0 := \{(\{A\}, \emptyset, \{A\}, \emptyset)\}$ 
2 while  $T_0$  do
3    $T := \text{Defensive-Nonredundant}(T_0)$ 
4   if  $T = \emptyset$  then
5      $\perp$  break;
6   else
7     find a tuple  $t = (\emptyset, \emptyset, DE, AT) \in T$ 
8      $I_0 := \{(\emptyset, \{B\}, \emptyset, \emptyset) \mid B \in DE\}$ 
9      $I := \text{FullTree}(I_0)$ 
10    if  $I = \emptyset$  then
11       $\perp$  break;
12    else  $T_0 := T \setminus \{t\}$ 
13 return  $T$ 

```

The following result sanctions the soundness of sceptical acceptance.

Theorem 6. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ drawn from δ such that it is ideal, then*

- δ is sceptically-successful;
- ϕ is sceptically accepted under **sem** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$), where $\mathbf{sem} \in \{\mathbf{adm}, \mathbf{prf}\}$.

The proof of this theorem is in Appendix B.

Theorem 7 presents the completeness.

Theorem 7. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is sceptically accepted under **sem** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$), where $\mathbf{sem} \in \{\mathbf{adm}, \mathbf{prf}\}$, and δ is sceptically-successful, then there is an ideal dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ drawn from δ .*

The proof of this theorem is in Appendix C.

5.3 Computing Grounded Acceptance

We discuss the computation of grounded acceptance for a formula. Observe that grounded semantics distinguishes itself from the remaining semantics by the fact that it has a unique extension, which can be efficiently computed in polynomial time via iteratively collecting singleton potential arguments defended from the empty set of potential arguments until a fixed point is reached. To determine the grounded acceptance, we use the following polynomial-time algorithm:

1. computes a grounded extension, and
2. verifies whether potential arguments for ϕ are accepted under the grounded extension.

For (1) and (2), we represent the following "winning conditions" for a *groundedly successful dialogue*: One requires that whenever \mathbf{O} could advance any evidence, \mathbf{P} still wins. This requirement is incorporated in dialogue trees being *defensive*. Note that credulously successful dialogues for computing credulous acceptance also require dialogue trees to be defensive (by Theorem 2). However, the credulously successful dialogues cannot be used to compute the grounded acceptance, as shown by Example 14. In Example 14, it would be incorrect to infer from the depicted credulously successful dialogue that $A(a)$ is groundedly accepted as the grounded extension is empty. Note that the dialogue tree for $A(a)$ is infinite. From this observation, it follows that the credulously successful dialogues are not sound for computing grounded acceptance. Since all dialogue trees of a formula that is credulously accepted but not groundedly accepted can be infinite, we could detect this situation by checking if constructed dialogue trees are infinite. This motivates us to consider "finite" dialogue trees as a winning condition. Thus, *defensive* and *finite* dialogue trees are required to determine grounded acceptance. In the next section, we present an algorithm for its computation.

5.3.1 ALGORITHMS

This section shows how an algorithm for computing the grounded acceptance is implemented. To perform Step (1) and (2), the algorithm constructs a defensive and finite dialogue tree for a potential argument A for ϕ . However, to check the finiteness of the defensive dialogue trees, the algorithm needs to check if graphs induced from the dialogue tree are acyclic. As a graph is acyclic iff its transitive closure does not contain any self-loop, this check can rely on an algorithm for computing transitive closures presented in (Thang, Dung, & Hung, 2009). For the reader's convenience, we reproduce the stepwise procedure of the **TransitiveClosure** algorithm tailored to P-SAFs, i.e., in the context of a hypergraph, as follows. Suppose at step i of a tree construction, the dialogue tree induces a graph G , and its transitive closure G^+ has been computed. The dialogue tree at step $i + 1$ induces a new graph $R = G \cup \Delta$ where $\Delta = \{(C, B) \mid C \in \mathcal{E} \text{ with } \mathcal{E} \text{ consists of newly presented arguments (i.e. } \mathcal{E} = \text{Attack}_B \text{ if } B \text{ is selected from } P_i \text{ and } \mathcal{E} = \{C\} \text{ if } B \text{ is selected from } O_i)\}$. Given G^+, \mathcal{E}, B as an input, the algorithm computes R^+ , by first setting $R^+ = G^+$, then correcting triples (X, Y, Z) that violate transitivity, i.e. $(X, Y), (Y, Z) \in R^+$ but $(X, Z) \notin R^+$. The correction proceeds in two steps: (i) Connect X to Z due to a new edge $(Y, Z) \in \Delta$, (ii) Connect X to Z due to X and B being connected by Step 1 or by Δ . We prefer to (Thang et al., 2009), p.24-25 for reading the algorithm in detail.

Lemma 3 (Lemma 12 (Thang et al., 2009)). *The TransitiveClosure algorithm has runtime $O(n^2)$.*

Using the TransitiveClosure algorithm, we present Algorithm 5 for a top-down construction of a defensive and finite tree whose root A is a potential argument for ϕ .

Algorithm 5: Defensive-Finite(T_0)

Input: A KB \mathcal{K} and $T_0 = \{(\{A\}, \emptyset, \{A\}, \emptyset)\}$ where A is a potential argument for ϕ

Output: A defensive and finite tree T

```

1 Initiate  $T := T_0$ 
2 while not (a tuple of  $T$  has the form  $(\emptyset, \emptyset, DE, AT, G^+)$ ) do
3   select  $t = (P, O, DE, AT, G^+) \in T$  and  $B \in P$  or  $B \in O$ 
4   remove  $t$  from  $T$ 
5   if  $B \in P$ , and no formulas  $\Delta \subseteq \text{Base}(\text{Attack}_B \cap DE)$  s.t.  $\Delta \cup \text{Base}(DE_i)$  is
      inconsistent, where  $\text{Attack}_B = \{\text{Attack}(B)\}$  then
6      $R^+ := \text{TransitiveClosure}(G^+, B, \text{Attack}_B)$ 
7     if  $R^+$  is acyclic then
8       add  $(P \setminus \{B\}, O \cup (\text{Attack}_B \setminus AT), DE, AT, R^+)$  to  $T$ 
9   if  $B \in O$  then
10    for each  $C \in \text{Attack}_B \setminus (AT \cup O)$  do
11       $R^+ := \text{TransitiveClosure}(G^+, B, \{C\})$ 
12      if  $R^+$  is acyclic then
13        add  $(P \cup \{C\}, O \setminus \{B\}, DE \cup \{C\}, AT \cup \{B\}, R^+)$  to  $T$ 
14 return  $T$ 

```

The following theorem establishes the soundness of grounded acceptance.

Theorem 8. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ such that it is defensive and finite, then*

- δ is groundedly-successful;
- ϕ is groundedly accepted under grounded semantics in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$).

The proof of this theorem is in Appendix B.

Theorem 9 presents the completeness of grounded acceptances.

Theorem 9. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is groundedly accepted under **grd** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$) and δ is groundedly-successful, then there is a defensive and finite dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .*

The proof of this theorem is in Appendix C.

5.4 Results for a Link between Inconsistency-Tolerant Reasoning and Dialogues

In Section 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, we have demonstrated the use of dialogue trees to determine the acceptance of a formula in the P-SAF drawn from the dialogue tree. As a direct corollary of Theorem 1 - 9, we show how to determine and explain the entailment of a formula in KBs by using dialogue trees, which was the main goal of this paper.

Corollary 1. *Let \mathcal{K} be a KB and ϕ be a formula in \mathcal{L} . Then ϕ is entailed in*

- *some maximal consistent subset of \mathcal{K} iff there is a defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ .*
- *the intersection of maximal consistent subsets of \mathcal{K} iff there is a defensive and finite dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ .*
- *all maximal consistent subsets of \mathcal{K} iff there is an ideal dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ .*

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Appendix A. Preliminaries

To prove the soundness and completeness, we sketch out **a general strategy** as follows:

1. Our proof starts with the observation that a dialogue δ for a formula ϕ can be seen as a collection of several (independent) focused sub-dialogues $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_n$. The dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from δ_i is a subtree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ drawn from the sub-dialogue δ , and it corresponds to the *abstract dialogue tree* that has root a potential argument for ϕ . (The notion of abstract dialogue tree can be found in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)). Thus it is necessary to consider a *correspondence principle* that links dialogue trees to abstract dialogue trees. The materials for this step can be found in Section A.2 and A.3.
2. The correspondence principle allows us to utilize the results of abstract dialogue trees in [(Ho & Schlobach, 2024), Corollary 1] to prove the soundness results. We extend Corollary 1 of (Ho & Schlobach, 2024) to prove the completeness results.

The proof of the soundness and completeness depends on some notions and results that we describe next.

Notation A.1. Let \mathcal{K} be a KB, $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{K}$ be a set of facts, and $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \text{Arg}_{\mathcal{K}}$ be a set of arguments induced from \mathcal{K} . Then,

- An argument B is a subargument of argument A iff $\text{Sup}(B) \subseteq \text{Sup}(A)$. We denote the set of subarguments of A as $\text{Subs}(A)$.

A.1 Abstract Dialogue Trees and Abstract Dialogue Forests

We observe that a formula ϕ can have many potential arguments for ϕ . Thus a dialogue tree with root ϕ can correspond to one, none, or multiple *abstract dialogue trees*, one for each potential argument for ϕ . We call this set of abstract dialogue trees an *abstract dialogue forest*. The following one presents a definition of abstract dialogue forests and reproduces a definition of abstract dialogue trees (analogous to Definition 8 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)). Formally:

Definition A.1 (Abstract dialogue forests). Let $\mathcal{AF}_{\delta} = (\text{Arg}_{\delta}, \text{Att}_{\delta})$ be the P-SAF drawn from a dialogue $D(\phi) = \delta$. An abstract dialogue forest (obtained from \mathcal{AF}_{δ}) for ϕ is a

set of abstract dialogue trees, written $\mathcal{F}_G(\phi) = \{\mathcal{T}_G^1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_G^h\}$, such that: For each abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^j ($j = 1, \dots, h$),

- the root of \mathcal{T}_G^j is the proponent argument (in \mathbf{Arg}_δ) with the conclusion ϕ ,
- if a node A in \mathcal{T}_G^j is a proponent argument (in \mathbf{Arg}_δ), then all its children (possibly none) are opponent arguments (in \mathbf{Arg}_δ) that attack A
- if a node A in \mathcal{T}_G^j is an opponent argument (in \mathbf{Arg}_δ), then exactly one of the following is true: (1) A has exactly one child, and this child is a proponent argument (in \mathbf{Arg}_δ) that attacks A ; (2) A has more than one child, and all these children are proponent arguments (in \mathbf{Arg}_δ) that collectively attacks A .

Remark 8. We call the abstract dialogue tree that has root an argument with conclusion ϕ an abstract dialogue tree for ϕ .

Fix an abstract dialogue forest $\mathcal{F}_G(\phi) = \{\mathcal{T}_G^1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_G^h\}$. For such abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^j ($i = 1, \dots, h$), we adopt the following conventions:

- Let \mathcal{B}_1 be the set of all proponent arguments in \mathcal{T}_G^j . $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^j) = \{\alpha \mid \forall A \in \mathcal{B}_1, \alpha \in \mathbf{Sup}(A)\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ is the *defence set* of \mathcal{T}_G^j , i.e. the set of facts in the support of the arguments in \mathcal{B}_1 .
- Similarly, let \mathcal{B}_2 be the set of all opponent arguments in \mathcal{T}_G^j . $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G^j) = \{\beta \mid \forall B \in \mathcal{B}_2, \beta \in \mathbf{Sup}(B)\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ is the *culprit set* of \mathcal{T}_G^j , i.e. the set of facts in support of the arguments in \mathcal{B}_2 .

We reproduce a definition of *admissible abstract dialogue trees* given in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024). This notion will be needed for Section A.3.

Definition A.2 (Admissible abstract dialogue trees). *An abstract dialogue tree for ϕ is said to be admissible iff the proponent wins and no argument labels both a proponent and an opponent node.*

Intuitively, in an abstract dialogue tree, a proponent wins if either the tree ends with arguments labelled by proponent nodes or every argument labelling an opponent node has a child.

A.2 Partitioning a Dialogue Tree into Focused Subtrees

This section shows how to partition a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ into focused subtrees of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. We will need this result to prove soundness and completeness results.

We observe that a dialogue $D(\phi) = \delta$, from which the dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is drawn, may contain one, none, or multiple *focused sub-dialogues* δ_i of δ . Each dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from the focused sub-dialogue δ_i is a subtree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ and focused. This is proven in the following lemma.

Lemma A.1. *Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a dialogue tree (with root ϕ) drawn from a dialogue $D(\phi) = \delta$. Every focused subtree of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ with root ϕ is the dialogue tree drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .*

Proof. All the subtrees considered in this proof are assumed to have root ϕ . The proof proceeds as follows:

1. First, we construct the set of focused dialogue subtrees of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$
2. Second, we show that each focused subtree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .

Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1), \dots, \mathcal{T}(\delta_m)$ be all the focused subtrees contained in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ with root ϕ . Each focused subtree is obtained in the following way: First, choose a single utterance at the root and discard the subtrees corresponding to the other utterances at the root. Then proceed (depth first) and for each potential argument labelled **O** with children labelled **P**, choose a single identifier and select among them those (and only those) with that identifier; discard the other children labelled **P** (which have a different identifier) and the corresponding subtrees. By Definition 17, every focused subtree can be obtained in this way.

2. We next prove (2) by showing the construction of the focused sub-dialogue δ_i that draws $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$.

Given m dialogue trees $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1), \dots, \mathcal{T}(\delta_m)$ constructed from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$, the focused sub-dialogue δ_i ($1 \leq i \leq m$) drawing the dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is constructed as follows:

- δ_i is initialised to empty;
- for each node $\psi, [-, -, \text{id}] = N$ in $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$,
 - if $u_{id} = (-, \text{ta}, -, \text{id})$ is in δ but not in δ_i , then add u_{id} to δ_i ;
 - let u_{ta} be the utterance in δ ; if u_{ta} is the target utterance of u_{id} , then add u_{ta} to δ_i ;
- Sort δ_i in the order of utterances ID .

It is easy to see that each δ_i constructed as above is a focused sub-dialogue of δ (by the definition of focused sub-dialogues in Definition 16), and $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is drawn from δ_i . Thus (2) is proved. \square

A.3 Transformation from Dialogue Trees into Abstract Dialogue Trees

The following *correspondence principle* allows to translate dialogue trees into abstract dialogue trees and vice versa.

Remark 9. Recall that a dialogue tree for ϕ has root ϕ , while an abstract dialogue tree for ϕ has root an argument for ϕ .

Theorem 10 (Correspondence principle). *Let $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ be a formula. Then:*

1. For every defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ , there exists an admissible abstract dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}$ for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}) \subseteq \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}) \subseteq \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$.

2. For every admissible abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G for ϕ , there exists a defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta)) \subseteq \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G)$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta)) \subseteq \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G)$.

Proof. We prove the theorem by transforming dialogue trees into abstract dialogue trees and vice versa.

1. The transformation from dialogue trees into abstract dialogue trees

Given a defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ with root ϕ , its equivalent abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G for an argument for ϕ in $\mathcal{T}_G^1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_G^h$ is constructed inductively as follows:

1. Modify $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ by adding a new *flag* (0 or 1) to nodes in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ and initialise 0 for all nodes; a node looks like $(-, [-, -, -]) - 0$. The obtained tree is $\mathcal{T}'(\delta)$.
2. \mathcal{T}_G is \mathcal{T}_G^h in the sequence $\mathcal{T}_G^1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_G^h$ constructed inductively as follows:
 - a) Let A be the potential argument drawn from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ that contains root ϕ . \mathcal{T}_G^1 contains exactly one node that holds A and is labelled by P . Set the nodes in $\mathcal{T}'(\delta)$ that are in A to 1. The obtained tree is $\mathcal{T}'_1(\delta)$.
 - b) Let \mathcal{T}_G^k be the k -th tree, with $1 \leq k \leq h$. \mathcal{T}_G^{k+1} is expanded from \mathcal{T}_G^k by adding nodes $(L : B_j)$ with $L \in \{P, 0\}$.
 For each node $(L : B_j)$, B_j is a potential argument drawn from $\mathcal{T}'_k(\delta)$, which is a child of C - another potential argument drawn from $\mathcal{T}'_k(\delta)$, such that:
 - there is at least one node in B_j that is assigned 0;
 - the root of B_j has a parent node t in $\mathcal{T}'_k(\delta)$ such that the flag of t is 1 and t is in C ;
 - if the root of B_j is labelled by P , then L is P . Otherwise, L is 0 .
 - set all nodes in $\mathcal{T}'_k(\delta)$ that are also in B_j to 1. The obtained tree is $\mathcal{T}'_{k+1}(\delta)$.
3. h is the smallest index s.t there is no node in $\mathcal{T}'_h(\delta)$ where its flag is 0.

\mathcal{T}_G is constructed as follows:

- Every node of $\mathcal{T}_G = \mathcal{T}_G^h$ includes a potential argument. For each potential argument, there is a unique node in \mathcal{T}_G . Each node is labelled P or 0 as potential arguments drawn from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ are labelled either P or 0 .
- The root of \mathcal{T}_G includes the potential argument for ϕ of the dialogue and labelled P by constructing $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$.
- Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is defensive, by Definition 19, it is focused and patient. Thus there is only one way of attacking a potential argument labelled by 0 . Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is defensive, by Definition 19, it is last-word. Then there is no un-attacked (potential) argument labelled by 0 . From the above, it follows that every 0 node has exactly one P node as its child.
- Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is non-redundant, by Definition 20, no potential argument labels 0 and P .

Recall that, in $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$, the potential arguments labelling P (O, respectively) are called proponent arguments (opponent arguments, respectively).

It can be seen that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ has the following properties:

- the root is the proponent argument for ϕ .
- the O node has either exactly one child holding one proponent argument that attacks it or children holding the proponent arguments that collectively attack it.
- all leaves are nodes labelled by P, namely P wins and there is no node labelled by both P and O.

It follows immediately that $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is an admissible abstract dialogue tree (by the definition of abstract dialogue trees in Definition A.1 and Definition A.2).

Since $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ contains the same potential arguments as $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ and the arguments have the same P/O labelling in both $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$, we have $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$.

2. The transformation from abstract dialogue trees into dialogue trees

We first need to introduce some new concepts that together constitute the dialogue tree.

Definition A.3 (Support trees). *A support tree of a formula α is defined as follows:*

1. *The root is a proponent node labelled by α .*
2. *Let N be a proponent node labelled by σ . If σ is a fact, then either N has no children, or N has children that are opponent nodes labelled by β_k , $k = 1, \dots, n$ such that $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\sigma\}$ is inconsistent. If σ is a non-fact, then one of the following holds:*
 - *either (1) N has children that are proponent nodes labelling ω_l , $l = 1, \dots, m$, such that $\sigma \in \text{CN}(\{\omega_l\})$,*
 - *or (2) N has children that are opponent nodes labelling β_k , $k = 1, \dots, n$, such that $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\sigma\}$ is inconsistent,*
 - *or both (1) and (2) hold.*

Definition A.4 (Context trees). *A context tree of a formula α is defined as follows:*

1. *The root is an opponent node labelled by α .*
2. *Let N be an opponent node labelled by σ . If σ is a fact, then N has children that are proponent nodes labelled by β_k , with $k = 1, \dots, n$, such that $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\sigma\}$ is inconsistent and the children have the same identify⁹. If σ is a non-fact, then one of the following holds:*
 - *either (1) N has children that are opponent nodes labelled by ω_l , with $l = 1, \dots, m$, such that $\sigma \in \text{CN}(\{\omega_l\})$,*
 - *or (2) N has children that are proponent nodes labelling β_k , with $k = 1, \dots, n$, such that $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\sigma\}$ is inconsistent and the children have the same identify,*

9. The condition of "children having the same identify" ensure that a potential argument is attacked by exactly one potential argument if $k = 1$ or collectively attacked by one set of potential arguments if $k > 1$.

- or both (1) and (2) hold.

Now we prove the translation from abstract dialogue trees to dialogue trees.

Given an abstract dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ for ϕ , its equivalent focused subtree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ of a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ is constructed inductively as follows:

Let $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}})$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}})$ be the defence set and the set of culprits of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$, respectively.

For each $\alpha \in \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}})$, let $arg(\beta_k)$, with $k = 1, \dots, n$, be a set of arguments for β_k labelling nodes in $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ such that $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\alpha\}$ is inconsistent. If $k = 1$, then there exists a single argument for β that attacks an argument including α . We say that an argument including α is an argument whose conclusion or support includes α . If $k > 1$, then there exists a set of arguments for β_k that collectively attacks an argument including α .

For each $\alpha \in \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}})$, let B_k^α be the set of facts in the support of arguments for β_k in $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ such that the arguments for β_k attack an argument including α . Clearly, there exists an argument for β that attacks an argument including α if $k = 1$ and there exist arguments for β_k that attack or collectively attack an argument including α if $k > 1$.

We construct inductively the sequence of trees $\mathcal{T}^1(\delta_i), \dots, \mathcal{T}^h(\delta_i)$ as follows:

1. $\mathcal{T}^1(\delta_i)$ is a support tree of ϕ corresponding to the argument labelling the root of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$.
2. Let $j = 2n$ such that the non-terminal nodes in the frontier of $\mathcal{T}^j(\delta_i)$ are opponent nodes labelled by a set of formulas β_k where $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\alpha\}$ is inconsistent and $\alpha \in \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}})$. Expand each such node by a context tree of β_k wrt B_k^α . The obtained tree is $\mathcal{T}^{j+1}(\delta_i)$.
3. Let $j = 2n+1$ such that the non-terminal nodes in the frontier of $\mathcal{T}^j(\delta_i)$ are proponent nodes labelled by a set of formula β_k , where $\{\beta_k\} \cup \{\alpha\}$ is inconsistent and $\alpha \in \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}})$. Expand each such node by a support tree of β_k corresponding to the argument for β_k . The obtained tree is $\mathcal{T}^{j+1}(\delta_i)$.
4. Define $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ to be the limit of $\mathcal{T}^j(\delta_i)$.

It follows immediately that $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is a dialogue tree for ϕ whose defence set is a subset of the defence set of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ and whose the culprit set is a subset of the culprit set of $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$. Since $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is admissible, by Definition A.2, the proponent wins, namely either the tree ends with arguments labelled by proponent nodes or every argument labelled by an opponent node has a child. By Definition 19, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive. Since $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ is admissible, by Definition A.2, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{G}}$ has no argument labelling both a proponent and an opponent node. By Definition 20, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is non-redundant. □

A.4 Notions and Results of Acceptance of an Argument from Its Abstract Dialogue Trees

For reader's convenience, we reproduce here definitions and results for abstract dialogues for ϕ that can also be found in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024). We use a similar argument for focused sub-dialogues of a dialogue δ for ϕ . In fact, the definitions and the results we reproduce here are essentially the same with abstract dialogues replaced by focused sub-dialogues of δ for ϕ . This replacement is because an abstract dialogue for ϕ can be seen as a focused sub-dialogue of a dialogue δ for ϕ . This follows immediately from the results in Lemma A.1

(i.e., showing a dialogue tree drawn from a dialogue δ for ϕ can be divided into focused subtrees drawn from focused sub-dialogues of δ for ϕ) and in Theorem 10 (i.e., showing each such focused subtrees corresponds with an abstract dialogue tree drawn from an abstract dialogue).

Definition A.5 (Analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)). *Let $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}$ be the abstract dialogue tree drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ' of a dialogue for ϕ . The focused sub-dialogue δ' is called*

- admissible-successful iff $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}$ is admissible;
- preferred-successful iff it is admissible-successful;
- grounded-successful iff $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}$ is admissible and finite;
- sceptical-successful iff $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}$ is admissible and for no opponent node in it, there exists an admissible dialogue tree for the argument labelling an opponent node.

Corollary 2 (Analogous to Corollary 1 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)). *Let \mathcal{K} be a KB, $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ a formula and $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$ be the corresponding P-SAF of \mathcal{K} . Then, ϕ is*

- credulously accepted in some admissible/preferred extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$ if there is a focused sub-dialogue δ' of a dialogue for ϕ such that δ' is admissible/preferred-successful;
- groundedly accepted in a grounded extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$ if there is a focused sub-dialogue δ' of a dialogue for ϕ such that δ' is grounded-successful;
- sceptically accepted in all preferred extensions of $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$ if there is a focused sub-dialogue δ' of a dialogue for ϕ such that δ' is sceptical-successful.

Appendix B. Proofs for Soundness Results

We follow the general strategy to prove Theorem 2, 3, 8 and 6. In particular, we:

1. partition a dialogue tree for ϕ drawn from a dialogue δ into subtrees for ϕ drawn from the focused sub-dialogue of δ (by Lemma A.1),
2. use the correspondence principle to transfer each subtree for ϕ into an abstract dialogue tree for ϕ (by Theorem 10),
3. apply Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024) and Corollary 2 (analogous to Corollary 1 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024))) for abstract dialogue trees to prove the soundness results.

B.1 Proof of Theorem 2

Theorem 2. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ such that it is defensive and non-redundant, then*

- δ is admissible-successful;

- ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$).

Proof. Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a dialogue tree drawn from a dialogue δ for ϕ . Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1), \dots, \mathcal{T}(\delta_m)$ be sub-trees (with root ϕ) constructed from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. By Lemma A.1, we know all sub-trees $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ are the dialogue trees drawn from focused sub-dialogues δ_i , with $i = 1, \dots, m$, of δ and each such sub-tree is focused. We assume that $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive and non-redundant. By the correspondence principle of Theorem 10, there is an abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$.

For such abstract dialogue tree, let \mathcal{B} be a set of proponent arguments in \mathcal{T}_G^i , we prove that

1. \mathcal{B} attacks every attack against it and \mathcal{B} does not attack itself;
2. no argument in \mathcal{T}_G^i that labels both P or O.

Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive and non-redundant, we get the following statements:

- a) By Definition 19, it is focused. Then the root of \mathcal{T}_G^i hold a proponent argument for ϕ .
- b) By Definition 19, it is last-word. Then the proponent arguments in \mathcal{T}_G^i are leaf nodes, i.e., P wins. Thus, \mathcal{B} attacks every attack against it.
- c) By Definition 19, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ has no formulas α_h in opponent nodes belong to $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ such that $\{\alpha_h\} \cup \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ is inconsistent. $h = 0$ corresponds to the case that there is no potential argument, say A , such that $\{\alpha\}$ is the support of A and A attacks any potential arguments supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$. Similarly, for $h > 0$, there are no potential arguments collectively attacking any potential arguments supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$. Thus, \mathcal{B} does not attack itself.
- d) By Definition 20 of non-redundant trees, there is no argument in \mathcal{T}_G^i that labels both P or O.

It can be seen that (b) and (c) prove (1), and (d) proves (2). It follows that \mathcal{T}_G^i is admissible. This result directly follows from the definition of admissible abstract dialogue trees in Definition A.2 (analogous to those in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)). By Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), δ_i is admissible-successful in the P-SAF framework \mathcal{AF}_{δ_i} drawn from δ_i (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$).

Now, we need to show δ is admissible-successful. By Definition A.1, each tree in the abstract dialogue forest contains its own set of proponent arguments, namely, $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) \neq \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^l)$, with $1 \leq i, l \leq m, i \neq l$. Thus, arguments in other trees do not affect arguments in \mathcal{AF}_{δ_i} . It follows that δ is admissible-successful. By Corollary 2 (analogous to Corollary 1 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** semantics in \mathcal{AF}_δ . \square

B.2 Proof of Theorem 8

The following lemma is used in the proof of Theorem 8

Lemma B.1. *An abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G is finite iff the set of arguments labelling P in \mathcal{T}_G is a subset of the grounded set of arguments.*

Proof. Let \mathcal{B} is a set of arguments labelling P in \mathcal{T}_{G} . We prove the lemma as follows:

If part: The height of a finite dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_{G} is $2h$. We prove that \mathcal{B} is a subset of the grounded set by induction on h . Observe that (1) if $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2$ are an admissible subset of the grounded set, then so is $\mathcal{A}_1 \cup \mathcal{A}_2$; (2) if an argument A is accepted wrt \mathcal{A}_1 then $\mathcal{A}_1 \cup \{A\}$ is an admissible subset of the grounded set.

$h = 0$ corresponds to dialogue trees containing a single node labelled by an argument that is not attacked. So \mathcal{B} containing only that argument is a subset of the grounded set.

Assume the assertion holds for all finite dialogue tree of height smaller than $2h$. Let A be an argument labelling P at the root of \mathcal{T}_{G} . For each argument B attacking a child of A , let \mathcal{T}_B be the subtree of \mathcal{T}_{G} rooted at B . Clearly, \mathcal{T}_B is a finite dispute tree with height smaller than $2h$. The union of sets of arguments labelling P of all \mathcal{T}_B is a subset of the grounded set and defends A . So \mathcal{B} is a subset of the grounded set.

Only if part: to construct a finite abstract dialogue tree for a groundedly accepted argument in a finite P-SAF framework, we need the following lemma: In a finite P-SAF framework, the grounded set equals $\emptyset \cup \mathcal{F}(\emptyset) \cup \mathcal{F}^2(\emptyset) \cup \dots$. This lemma follows from two facts, proven in (Dung, 1995), of the characteristic function \mathcal{F} :

- \mathcal{F} is monotonic w.r.t. set inclusion.
- if the argument framework is finite, then \mathcal{F} is ω -continuous.

For each argument A in the grounded set, A can be ranked by a natural number $r(A)$ such that $A \in \mathcal{F}^{n(A)}(\emptyset) \setminus \mathcal{F}^{r(A)-1}(\emptyset)$. So $r(A) = 1$, then A belongs to the grounded set and is not attacked. $r(A) = 2$, the set of arguments (of the grounded set) defended by the set of arguments (of the grounded set) such that $r(A) \leq 1$ and so on. For each set of arguments \mathcal{S} collectively attacking the grounded set, the rank of \mathcal{S} is $\min\{r(A) \mid A \text{ is in the grounded set and attacks some argument in } \mathcal{S}\}$. Clearly, \mathcal{S} does not attack any argument in the grounded set of rank smaller than the rank of \mathcal{S} .

Given any argument A in the grounded set, we can build an abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_{G} for A as follows: The root of \mathcal{T}_{G} is labelled by A . For each set of arguments \mathcal{S} attacking A , we select a set of arguments \mathcal{C} to counterattacks \mathcal{S} such that the rank of \mathcal{C} equals the rank of \mathcal{S} , then for each set of arguments \mathcal{E} attacking some arguments of \mathcal{C} , we select arguments \mathcal{F} to counterattacks \mathcal{E} such that the rank of \mathcal{F} equals to the rank of \mathcal{E} , and so on. So for each branch of \mathcal{T}_{G} , the rank of a proponent node is equal to that of its opponent parent node, but the rank of an opponent node is smaller than that of its parent proponent node. Clearly, ranking decreases downwards. So all branches of \mathcal{T}_{G} are of finite length. Since the P-SAF is finite, \mathcal{T}_{G} is finite in breath. Thus \mathcal{T}_{G} is finite. □

Theorem 8. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ such that it is defensive and finite, then*

- δ is groundedly-successful;
- ϕ is groundedly accepted under grounded semantics in \mathcal{AF}_{δ} drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$).

Proof. Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a dialogue tree drawn from a dialogue δ for ϕ and $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1), \dots, \mathcal{T}(\delta_m)$ (with root ϕ) be subtrees of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. By Lemma A.1, all sub-trees of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ are the dialogue trees drawn from focused sub-dialogues δ_i , with $i = 1, \dots, m$, of δ and each such subtree is focused. Assume that $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive and finite. Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive, by the correspondence principle of Theorem 10, there is an abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$.

For such abstract dialogue tree, let \mathcal{B} be the set of arguments labelling P in \mathcal{T}_G^i . We need to show that

1. \mathcal{T}_G^i is finite;
2. \mathcal{B} attacks ever attract against it, and
3. \mathcal{B} does not attack itself.

Similar to the proof of Theorem 2, (2) and (3) directly follows from the fact that $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is admissible. Trivially, every $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is finite, then \mathcal{T}_G^i is finite. As a direct consequence of Lemma B.1, we obtain that \mathcal{B} is a subset of the grounded set of arguments in \mathcal{T}_G^i . By Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), δ_i is grounded-successful in \mathcal{AF}_{δ_i} (drawn from δ_i).

We next prove that δ is grounded-successful. Since δ_i is grounded-successful in \mathcal{AF}_{δ_i} drawn from δ_i , it follows that there are no arguments attacking the arguments in \mathcal{B} that have not been counter-attacked in the abstract dialogue forest $\mathcal{T}_G^1, \dots, \mathcal{T}_G^m$ (obtained from the P-SAF drawn from δ). By Definition A.1, each tree in the abstract dialogue forest contains its own set of proponent arguments, namely, $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) \neq \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^l)$, with $1 \leq i, l \leq m$, $i \neq l$. If the set of proponent arguments in \mathcal{T}_G^i drawn from the focused sub-dialogue δ_i is grounded, it is also grounded in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ . Thus, δ is grounded successful. By Corollary 2 (analogous to Corollary 1 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), ϕ is groundedly accepted in \mathcal{AF}_δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$). \square

B.3 Proof of Theorem 6

Theorem 6. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ drawn from δ such that it is ideal, then*

- δ is sceptically-successful;
- ϕ is sceptically accepted under **sem** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$, where **sem** \in {**adm**, **prf**}).

Proof. We prove this theorem for the case of admissible semantics. The proof for preferred (stable) semantics is analogous.

Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a dialogue tree drawn from a dialogue δ for ϕ , and $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1), \dots, \mathcal{T}(\delta_m)$ (with root ϕ) be subtrees constructed from $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. By Lemma A.1, we know all subtrees in $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ are dialogue trees drawn from focused sub-dialogues δ_i , ($i = 1, \dots, m$) of δ and each tree is focused. Assume that $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is ideal. Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is ideal, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is ideal. By Definition 21, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive. By the correspondence principle, there is an abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G^i) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$.

For such abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i , we need to show that:

1. \mathcal{T}_G^i is admissible, and
2. for no opponent node $\mathbf{0}$ in it there exists an admissible dialogue tree for the opponent argument.

Similar to the proof of Theorem 2, (1) holds. Since $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is ideal, by Definition 21, there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ such that none of the opponent arguments drawn from $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ belongs to an admissible set of arguments in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ . Then, (2) holds.

We have shown that \mathcal{T}_G^i is defensive and none of the opponent arguments belongs to an admissible set of arguments in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ . By Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), δ is sceptical-successful. By Corollary 2 (analogous to Corollary 1 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), ϕ is sceptically accepted in \mathcal{AF}_δ . \square

Appendix C. Proofs for Completeness Results

To prove the completeness results, we

1. partition a dialogue δ for ϕ into its focused sub-dialogues of δ (by Definition 16),
2. apply Corollary 3 and Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)) to obtain the existence of an abstract dialogue tree drawn from each focused sub-dialogue of δ wrt argumentation semantics,
3. use the correspondence principle to transfer from each abstract dialogue tree for ϕ into a dialogue tree for ϕ (by Theorem 10), thereby proving the completeness results.

C.1 Preliminaries

Corollary 2 is used for the proof of the soundness results. To prove the completeness result, we need to extend Corollary 2 as follows:

Corollary 3. *Let \mathcal{K} be a KB, $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ a formula and $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$ be the corresponding P-SAF of \mathcal{K} . We say that if ϕ is*

- *credulously accepted in some admissible/preferred extension of $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$, then there is a focused sub-dialogue δ_i , with $i = 1, \dots, m$, of a dialogue for ϕ such that δ_i is admissible/preferred-successful;*
- *groundedly accepted in a grounded extension of $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$, then there is a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of a dialogue for ϕ such that δ_i is grounded-successful;*
- *sceptically accepted in all preferred extensions of $\mathcal{AF}_\mathcal{K}$, then there is a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of a dialogue for ϕ such that δ_i is sceptical-successful.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ be a dialogue tree drawn from a dialogue δ for ϕ and $\mathcal{T}(\delta_1), \dots, \mathcal{T}(\delta_m)$ (with root ϕ) be subtrees of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$. By Lemma A.1, all sub-trees of $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ are the dialogue trees drawn from focused sub-dialogues δ_i , with $i = 1, \dots, m$, of δ and each such subtree is focused. By the correspondence principle, there is an abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for an

argument A with conclusion ϕ , or simply, an abstract dialogue $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i$ for ϕ , which corresponds to the dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ .

It is clear that there is a focused sub-dialogue δ_i such that it is admissible-successful if ϕ is credulously accepted in some admissible/preferred extension of $\mathcal{AF}_{\mathcal{K}}$. The argument given in Definition 2 and Lemma 1 of (Thang et al., 2009) for binary attacks generalizes to collective attacks, implying that A is accepted in some admissible extension iff $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i$ is admissible which in turn holds iff P wins and no argument labels both a proponent and an opponent node. By Definition A.5, δ_i is admissible-successful iff $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i$ is admissible. Thus, the statement is proved.

δ_i is preferred-successful if δ_i is admissible-successful. This result directly follows from the results of (Dung, 1995) that states that an extension is preferred if it is admissible. Thus, if ϕ is credulously accepted in some preferred extension, then δ_i is preferred-successful.

The other statement follows in a similar way as a straightforward generalization of Theorem 1 of (Thang et al., 2009) for the "grounded-successful" semantic; Definition 3.3 and Theorem 3.4 of (Dung et al., 2007) for the "sceptical-successful" semantic. \square

C.2 Proof of Theorem 4

Theorem 4. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_{δ} drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$) and δ is admissible-successful, then there is a defensive and non-redundant dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .*

Proof. Given δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$, we assume that ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_{δ} drawn from δ and δ is admissible-successful. We prove that there exists a dialogue tree drawn from the sub-dialogue of δ such that the dialogue tree is defensive and non-redundant.

Let $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_m$, where $i = 1, \dots, m$, be sub-dialogues of δ and each sub-dialogue is focused. Since ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_{δ} drawn from the dialogue δ , by Corollary 3, the focused sub-dialogue δ_i is admissible-successful. By Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), there is an admissible abstract dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i$ for ϕ drawn from the admissible-successful dialogue δ_i . By the correspondence principle, there exists a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ that corresponds to the abstract dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i$ for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i))$. Since $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{G}}^i$ is admissible, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive and non-redundant. Thus, the statement is proved. \square

C.3 Proof of Theorem 9

Theorem 9. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is groundedly accepted under **grd** in \mathcal{AF}_{δ} drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$) and δ is groundedly-successful, then there is a defensive and finite dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ drawn from a focused sub-dialogue δ_i of δ .*

Proof. Given δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$, we assume that ϕ is groundedly accepted under **grd** in \mathcal{AF}_{δ} drawn from δ and δ is groundedly-successful. We prove that there exists a dialogue tree drawn from the sub-dialogue of δ such that the dialogue tree is defensive and finite.

Let $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_m$, where $i = 1, \dots, m$, be sub-dialogues of δ and each sub-dialogue is focused. Since ϕ is groundedly accepted under **grd** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from the dialogue δ , by Corollary 3, the focused sub-dialogue δ_i is grounded-successful. By Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), there is an admissible and finite abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ drawn from the grounded-successful dialogue δ_i . By the correspondence principle, there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ that corresponds to the abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i)$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G^i)$. Since \mathcal{T}_G^i is admissible, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive. Since \mathcal{T}_G^i is finite, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is finite. Thus, the statement is proved. \square

C.4 Proof of Theorem 7

Theorem 7. *Let δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$. If ϕ is sceptically accepted under **sem** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ (supported by $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta))$), where **sem** \in $\{\text{adm}, \text{prf}\}$, and δ is sceptically-successful, then there is an ideal dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ drawn from δ .*

Proof. We prove this theorem for the case of admissible semantics. The proof for preferred (stable) semantics is analogous.

Given δ be a dialogue for a formula $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$, we assume that ϕ is credulously accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from δ and δ is admissible-successful. We prove that there is an ideal dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ for ϕ drawn from the dialogue δ .

Let $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_m$, where $i = 1, \dots, m$, be focused sub-dialogues of δ . Since ϕ is sceptically accepted under **adm** in \mathcal{AF}_δ drawn from the dialogue δ , by Corollary 3, the focused sub-dialogue δ_i is sceptical-successful. By Definition A.5 (analogous to Definition 9 in (Ho & Schlobach, 2024)), there is an abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ drawn from the sceptical-successful dialogue δ_i such that \mathcal{T}_G^i is admissible and for no opponent node in it there exists an admissible abstract dialogue tree for the argument labelling an opponent node. Since \mathcal{T}_G^i is admissible, by the correspondence principle, there is a dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ for ϕ that corresponds to the abstract dialogue tree \mathcal{T}_G^i for ϕ such that $\mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \mathcal{DE}(\mathcal{T}_G^i)$ and $\mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)) = \mathcal{CU}(\mathcal{T}_G^i)$.

For such the dialogue tree $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$, we need to show that:

1. $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is defensive and non-redundant,
2. none of the opponent arguments obtained from $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ belongs to an admissible set of potential arguments in \mathcal{AF}_{δ_i} drawn from $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$.

Since the abstract dialogue \mathcal{T}_G^i is admissible, (1) holds. We have that, for no opponent node in \mathcal{T}_G^i , there exists an admissible abstract dialogue tree for the argument labelling by 0. From this, we obtain that (2) holds. By Definition 21, $\mathcal{T}(\delta_i)$ is ideal. Thus, $\mathcal{T}(\delta)$ is ideal. Thus, the statement is proved. \square